

Climate sensitivity, commitment and abrupt change: toward an ontology for climate tipping point research

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Abstract

We review a number of notions in tipping point research that have been studied within work package 6 of the TiPES project and sketch how to organise them in a prototype ontology. For *climate sensitivity* and *climate change commitment*, we propose an operational semantics by giving their generic computational structure.

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1 Introduction

This short report is concerned with selected notions that are relevant in the context of *tipping point* research as conducted within the EU Horizon 2020 project TiPES (**T**ipping **P**oints in the **E**arth **S**ystem) [23]. The focus lies on the following notions:

- *Climate Sensitivity* (Section 4)
- *Commitment* (Section 5)
- *Abrupt climate change*, *Tipping Point (TP)* and *Tipping element (TE)* (Section 6)
- *Early Warning Signal (EWS)* (Section 7)

To explore these notions, we proceed as follows: We briefly give some general context (Section 2) and introduce a few abstract language elements to facilitate talking about models, simulations and data (Section 3). For each notion (Sections 4–7) we give a brief overview as introduction and collect (possibly informal) definitions and classification information that may be used as semantic annotation. We also assemble references for further reading that allow to follow the development of the notion in question. For climate sensitivity and commitment experiments, we suggest generic computational schemes of which these experiments are instances, following the approach of [Ion09; Ion16]. Our main motivation is ontological: How are the notions defined and used in the literature? What is their computational structure, which input and output types do they have, which physical dimensions (if applicable) and how are they related to other notions? In Section 8 we sketch an abstract perspective that may help to organise tipping point notions in the style of an ontology.

Figure 1: TiPES work package topics

Remarks: The report is part of Deliverable 6.2 of TiPES WP6. In the context of WP6’s objectives, it is meant to serve as preparation of a *domain specific language (DSL)* with tipping point notions. This DSL is to be implemented as extension of the *IdrisLibs* framework for the study of sequential decision problems [Bot21].¹

¹The framework is implemented in *Idris*, a dependently typed programming language that allows to specify, implement and prove properties of programs all in one language.

The choice of the notions discussed in this report is guided by the topics studied in TiPES WP1–5 (see Fig.1 and cf. Appendix II for reference). We include pointers in text passages that relate to these work packages’ objectives (e.g. concerning the classical notion of *equilibrium climate sensitivity*). Parts of this work might also be understood as an elaboration of some entries of the *Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)* glossary (its most recent version can be found in Appendix VII of the AR6 WGI report [Mas+21; Mat+21]) without the ambition of achieving the generality of the relevant chapters of the IPCC assessment reports. For reference, we have included a number of glossary entries which concern our notions of interest in Appendix I. Other general sources we found helpful in the preparation of this document are course materials/resulting textbooks [Goo+10; Goo15; Sto11] and the recent overview paper [GL20].

2 Preliminaries

Central notions underlying everything we will be discussing subsequently are those of *climate system* and *Earth system*.

2.1 Climate and Earth system

First of all: what is a *system*? Wikipedia tells us that

“A system is a group of interacting or interrelated elements that act according to a set of rules to form a unified whole. [Mer] A system, surrounded and influenced by its environment, is described by its boundaries, structure and purpose and expressed in its functioning. Systems are the subjects of study of systems theory.” (*citation adapted*)

and

”In engineering and physics, a physical system is the portion of the universe that is being studied (of which a thermodynamic system is one major example). ”

and also

“Systems theory views the world as a complex system of interconnected parts. One scopes a system by defining its boundary; this means choosing which entities are inside the system and which are outside—part of the environment. One can make simplified representations (models) of the system in order to understand it and to predict or impact its future behavior. These models may define the structure and behavior of the system.”

The TiPES project is concerned with tipping elements in the *Earth System* of which the *climate system* forms a subsystem. The *climate system* consists itself of five major subsystems, namely the atmosphere, hydrosphere, cryosphere, lithosphere and biosphere. The notion of *Earth system* in the context of *Earth System Science* [Com86; Com88; Mos06] is broader and in particular includes human societies as subsystems. The notions discussed in this document mostly have emerged from the study of the climate system, and the influence of human societies is usually considered as external *forcing* applied to the system, e.g. via anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. However, in Section 6 we will e.g. encounter the notion of *policy-relevant tipping element* which explicitly includes human *value judgements* and seeks to encompass tipping behaviour beyond bio-physical processes.

The IPCC glossary does not give a definition of *Earth System*, but a definition of *Climate System*.

IPCC Glossary: Climate system

The global system consisting of five major components: the atmosphere, the hydrosphere, the cryosphere, the lithosphere and the biosphere and the interactions between them. The climate system changes in time under the influence of its own internal dynamics and because of external forcings such as volcanic eruptions, solar variations, orbital forcing, and anthropogenic forcings such as the changing composition

of the atmosphere and land-use change.

The IPCC considers the climate system as a dynamical system:

IPCC Glossary: Dynamical system

A process or set of processes whose evolution in time is governed by a set of deterministic physical laws. The climate system is a dynamical system.

Ghil and Lucarini begin their paper on the physics of climate change [GL20] with the statement:

“The climate system is forced, dissipative, chaotic, and out of equilibrium; its complex natural variability arises from the interplay of positive and negative feedbacks, instabilities, and saturation mechanisms.”

and later:

“A key goal of climate modelling is to capture the system’s statistical properties, i.e., its mean state and its variability, and its response to forcings of a different nature.”

Accordingly, most of the notions we will discuss in this report are closely linked to studying the climate system as a dynamical system and its response to interventions of some form.

Because of the complexity of this system and the very limited possibility/ quasi impossibility to study it via systematic and repeatable empirical experiments, the main methodologies are based on physical theories and numerical simulations with *models*. There is a whole hierarchy of models, ranging from simple conceptual to complex global or regional models.

The study via models and model simulations is complemented with the analysis of data in the form of time series. The data either comes from *the instrumental record*² or from historical *proxies*. The outcome of assessments of climate system properties depends on the model and/or data used, and on additional assumptions that are made to fill gaps in the knowledge or simplifications necessary for computational feasibility.

Data sources can be classified according to the *time scales* for which they provide information. A rough orientation following Fig. 2 of [KR15]:

Timescales and different kinds of data

- Observations: years to decades
- GCM simulations: years to centuries (few to couple thousands of years)
- Paleo proxies: decades to hundreds of millions of years

Differences in the *time scale* of processes in the climate system can be formalised using the mathematical theory of *slow-fast systems* [Kue11].

2.2 Classification of climate models

Climate models can be classified according to features like which components they contain as sub-models and the number of space dimensions. In more detail one can consider the components of the state space, the parameters, possible forcings and boundary conditions, but also aspects of computer implementations for numerical simulations. One speaks of a *model hierarchy* referring to the increase/decrease of complexity between different classes of models. The IPCC list on the lowest

²going back only a few hundred years, with systematic measurements starting in the second half of the 19th century

level of this hierarchy a class of *Simple Climate Models (SCMs)*, like *Energy Balance Models (EBMs)* or *ocean box models*. This class of models is used to study specific aspects of the climate system in a stylised way. On the highest level of the hierarchy one finds *Global Climate Models/General Circulation Models (GCMs)* and *Earth System Models (ESMs)*. These models aim at a best possible representation of (bio)-physical processes. Integrating these models however comes with a high computational cost and thus it is not feasible to run huge ensembles of simulations for different scenarios. Another approach that seeks to combine advantages of simple and complex models is provided by *Earth system models of Intermediate Complexity (EMICs)*.

Another way to distinguish different types of models is to classify them as *process-based*, *statistical* or *conceptual* models [Goo15; Cru12]. An overview over Earth system models is given in [Fla11].

An important example of the simplest class of models is the *Stommel box model* [Sto61] of the *thermohaline circulation (THC)* in the North Atlantic. It illustrates the northward transport at the surface of the ocean of relatively warm and salty waters which then cool down, sink and are transported back southward in the depth of the ocean. The THC is considered a [tipping element](#) and the Stommel model is an early example of a [model with more than one stable state](#). The model and its variants have been and are still used in many studies (e.g. recently in [Alk+19; Loh+21; KLN22]).

Example 1. (*Stommel box model variant following [Mar00] and [Goo+10]*)

The model consists of two “well-mixed boxes of equal volume” B_1 and B_2 , containing water having a certain temperature and a certain salinity. Box B_1 represents the ocean at high latitudes and B_2 the ocean at lower latitudes. In the simplest variant of the model, the temperatures of the two boxes are not part of the dynamics but given as parameters.

The dynamic variables then are just $S_1, S_2 : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ representing the temporal evolution of the salinity of B_1 and B_2 , respectively ³

The model has the following parameters:

- $T_1, T_2 : \mathbb{R}$ – temperatures of boxes B_1 and B_2 , respectively, with the condition that $T_2 > T_1$ (corresponding to lower temperatures at higher latitudes) ($[T_1] = [T_2] = \Theta$)⁴
- $k : \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ – a hydraulic constant ($[k] = \text{L}^3\text{M}^{-1}$)
- $\alpha : \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ – the thermal expansion coefficient ($[\alpha] = \text{L}^{-3}\text{M}\Theta^{-1}$)
- $\beta : \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ – the haline contraction coefficient ($[\beta] = \text{L}^{-3}\text{M}$)
- $H : \mathbb{R}$ – represents the surface salinity flux when positive and surface freshwater flux when negative (i.e. positive freshwater flux is presented as negative salinity flux) ($[H] = \text{T}^{-1}\text{L}^3$)

Two assumptions are made concerning the density of the water in the boxes and the flow between the boxes:

- the density of the water in each box can be approximated by a linear function $\rho : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ of its salinity $s : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and temperature $T : \mathbb{R}$

$$\rho(s, T) = \rho_0 - \alpha * (T - T_0) + \beta * (s - s_0)$$

where s_0, T_0 and ρ_0 are salinity, temperature and salinity at a reference state ($[\rho(s, T)] = \text{L}^{-3}\text{M}$)

- the strength of the salinity flow $q_{B_1 \rightarrow B_2} : \mathbb{R}$ between the two boxes (with densities $\rho_1, \rho_2 : \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, respectively) is proportional to their density difference:

$$q_{B_1 \rightarrow B_2} = k * (\rho_1 - \rho_2) \tag{1}$$

³In an alternative formulation of the model there is only one dynamic variable representing the salinity difference between the two boxes.

⁴The bracket notation $[\cdot]$ is used to indicate physical dimension. Please see the paragraph “Physical dimensions” [below](#) for a discussion.

If $s_1, s_2 : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ are the salinities of the boxes, by combining these two assumptions one gets for $i \in \{1, 2\}$:

$$\rho_i = \rho(s_i, T_i) = \rho_0 - \alpha * (T_i - T_0) + \beta * (s_i - S_0)$$

and thus

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_1 - \rho_2 &= \rho_0 - \alpha * (T_1 - T_0) + \beta * (s_1 - S_0) - (\rho_0 - \alpha * (T_2 - T_0) + \beta * (s_2 - S_0)) \\ &= \alpha * (T_2 - T_1) + \beta * (s_2 - s_1) \end{aligned}$$

Writing $\Delta T = T_2 - T_1$ for the difference between the box water temperatures that are given as parameters, and using the above assumptions, the salinity flow strength between the two boxes at some point in time $t : \mathbb{R}$ can then be computed via a function $q : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ given their salinity difference $\Delta S(t) = S_2(t) - S_1(t)$ at time t :

$$q(\Delta S(t)) = k * (\alpha * \Delta T - \beta * \Delta S(t))$$

If $q > 0$, the direction of the salinity flow is from low to high latitudes at the surface and from high to low at the bottom of the ocean (this corresponds to the current situation in the North Atlantic.) The state of the model represents the salinities of the two boxes. The equations that specify their temporal evolutions $S_1, S_2 : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ are:

$$\frac{dS_1}{dt}(t) = -H + |q(\Delta S(t))| * \Delta S(t) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dS_2}{dt}(t) = +H - |q(\Delta S(t))| * \Delta S(t) \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta S(t) = S_2(t) - S_1(t)$. That is, the change in salinity at time t depends on the surface salinity/freshwater flux and the product of the salinity flow strength between the two boxes and the salinity difference. Recall that box B_1 represents the cold water at high latitudes where the surface flux is a freshwater flux from meltwater (decreasing salinity). This is expressed in Eq. 2 as a negated salinity flux $-H$. For box B_2 the surface flux represents the evaporation at lower latitudes (increasing salinity). The flow strength is used as absolute value since the salinity balance of the boxes does not depend on whether the direction goes from B_1 to B_2 at the top and from B_2 to B_1 at the bottom or vice versa.

Assuming e.g. that the temperature difference is greater than the salinity difference between the two boxes (“temperature driven” situation), then, if the salinity of B_2 is higher than that of B_1 , this decreases both the rate of change of the salinity of B_1 and B_2 and the flow strength. Otherwise both are increased. Whether the overall rate of change is positive or negative then depends critically on the value of the parameter H , as does the existence of an equilibrium solution (this will be relevant in Section 6).

The interest of the model is to illustrate what is called the *salinity* or *ocean advection feedback*: If the circulation strength of the *thermohaline circulation (THC)* (that is represented by the strength of the salinity flow in the model) is decreased by a perturbation, less salinity is transported to higher latitudes. This results in lower density there, which in turn decreases the flow strength thereby reinforcing the initial perturbation.

Classification of climate models

Some criteria that may be used to classify models:

- process-based, statistical, conceptual, ...
- model classes:
 - Energy Balance Model (*EBM*),
 - Earth system model of Intermediate Complexity (*EMIC*),

- General Circulation/ Global Climate Models with representations of the atmosphere and/or the ocean (*AGCM*, *OGCM*, *AOGCM*)
- Earth System Model (*ESM*)
- Regional Climate Model (*RCM*),
- Ocean box model
- spatial dimensions: 0, 1, 2, 3
- *subsystems* of the climate system represented in the model: atmosphere, ocean, ice-sheets, carbon cycle, ...

Physical dimensions. Following a notation originally introduced by Maxwell and widely applied in textbooks, we write $[e] = d$ to denote that the physical quantity e has dimension d . For example, we write $[T] = \Theta$ to indicate that T has the dimension of a temperature.

Expressions like $[e] = d$ and $[T] = \Theta$ are called *dimensional judgements*, in analogy with *type judgements* like $q \in \mathbb{R}$ or $q : \mathbb{R}$.

Specifically, $[T] = \Theta$ is an abbreviation for $[T] = \lambda(\mathbb{T}, \mathbb{L}, \mathbb{M}, \Theta).\Theta$ and the anonymous function⁵ $\lambda(\mathbb{T}, \mathbb{L}, \mathbb{M}, \Theta).\Theta$ is called the *dimension function* of T . The judgement posits that measurements of T increase by Θ when the units of measurement for times, lengths, masses and temperatures are decreased by $\mathbb{T}, \mathbb{L}, \mathbb{M}, \Theta : \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, respectively, see [Bar+96] section 1.1.3.

Dimensional judgements are at the core of dimensional analysis and similarity theory [Buc14; Buc15; Bri22; Bar+96; Gib11] and build the basis of the mathematical modelling and of the data-based analysis of physical systems.

3 Framework

In this section we introduce a framework that we will use to describe computational structures in the remainder of the paper.

Model

A time-dependent climate model is given by a system of ODEs or PDEs:

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial t} = \mathcal{F}(p, m). \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{F} is a higher-order function

$$\mathcal{F} : P \times (\mathcal{T} \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow X) \rightarrow (\mathcal{T} \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow X') \quad d \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\} \quad (5)$$

that, together with parameters $p : P$ and suitable initial and, possibly, boundary conditions, implicitly defines a function $m : \mathcal{T} \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow X$.

Example 2. For an ODE of the form

$$\dot{m}(t) = f(p, t, m(t)) \quad (6)$$

with parameters $p : P$, time $t : \mathcal{T}$, functions $m : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow X$ and $f : P \times \mathcal{T} \times X \rightarrow X$ the higher order function \mathcal{F} in the above framework is defined by

$$\mathcal{F}(p, m) = \lambda t. f(p, t, m(t)).$$

⁵Note that we use the λ -notation to define anonymous functions in the sense of Church's λ -calculus [Bar+84] as common in the context of functional programming but also e.g. in [Python](#).)

Example 3. To express a PDE written

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial t} = m * \frac{\partial m}{\partial r_1} \quad (7)$$

in abbreviation for

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial t}(t, (r_1, r_2, r_3)) = m(t, (r_1, r_2, r_3)) * \frac{\partial m}{\partial r_1}(t, (r_1, r_2, r_3)) \quad (8)$$

with $t : \mathcal{T}$, $d = 3$, $(r_1, r_2, r_3) : \mathbb{R}^3$ and $m : \mathcal{T} \times \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow X$ in the above framework, we define

$$\mathcal{F}(p, m) = \lambda(t, (r_1, r_2, r_3)).m(t, (r_1, r_2, r_3)) * \frac{\partial m}{\partial r_1}(t, (r_1, r_2, r_3))$$

Example 4. (continuing Example 1)

For the Stommel model of Section 2, we can instantiate this scheme as follows:

- $\mathcal{T} = \mathbb{R}$, $d = 0$
- a state of the model represents the salinity of the two boxes at some point in time; the salinity cannot be negative: $X = \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^2$ ⁶
- thus the sought solution m is of type $\mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^2$
- the model is parameterised by constants $k, \alpha, \beta : \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ and $T_1, T_2, H : \mathbb{R}$, thus $P = \mathbb{R}_{>0}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3$. If we have a closer look at the defining equations, though, these parameters could actually be merged into just one.
- the strength of the flow is given by a function $q : P \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with

$$q(p, \Delta s) = k * (\alpha * \Delta T - \beta * \Delta s)$$

where $p = (k, \alpha, \beta, T_1, T_2, H)$ and $\Delta T = T_2 - T_1$.

- with $f : \mathbb{R}_{>0}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$

$$f(p, t, S_1, S_2) = (-H + |q(p, \Delta S)| * \Delta S, +H - |q(p, \Delta S)| * \Delta S)$$

where $\Delta S = S_2 - S_1$. Then $\mathcal{F}(p, m) = \lambda t.f(p, t, m(t))$ as above.

Dynamical Systems. As we have seen in the last section, to study its properties, the climate system is considered as a dynamical system. One may consider notions of dynamical systems of increasing complexity. We mention here *autonomous*, *nonautonomous* and *monadic* dynamical systems.

Following [Kuz13, Def.1.1]:

Autonomous Dynamical System

An *autonomous dynamical system* is a triple $(\mathcal{T}, X, \{\varphi^t\}_{t:\mathcal{T}})$, where \mathcal{T} is a time set, X is a state space, and $\{\varphi^t : X \rightarrow X\}_{t:\mathcal{T}}$ is a family of evolution operators satisfying the following properties:

$$\varphi^0 = id \quad (9)$$

$$\varphi^{t_1+t_2} = \varphi^{t_1} \circ \varphi^{t_2} \quad (10)$$

for all $x : X$, $t_1, t_2 : \mathcal{T}$ such that both sides of the equations are defined when applied to x (and where id is the identity function on X).

For continuous dynamical systems, the family of evolution operators $\{\varphi^t\}_{t:\mathcal{T}}$ is called a *flow*. Note that $\varphi^t(x)$ is not necessarily defined for all combinations of $t : \mathcal{T}$ and $x : X$.

Similarly, for nonautonomous systems (cf. [KR11, Def.2.1]):

⁶sometimes the dynamics is simply expressed for the salinity difference, in which case we simply have $X = \mathbb{R}$

Nonautonomous Dynamical System

An *nonautonomous dynamical system* is a triple $(\mathcal{T}, X, \{\varphi^t\}_{t:\mathcal{T}})$, where \mathcal{T} is a time set, X is a state space, and $\{\varphi^t : \mathcal{T} \times X \rightarrow X\}_{t:\mathcal{T}}$ is a family of evolution operators satisfying the following properties:

$$\varphi^0(t_0, \cdot) = id \quad \forall t_0 \in \mathcal{T} \quad (11)$$

$$\varphi^{t_1+t_2}(t_0, \cdot) = \varphi^{t_2}(t_0 + t_1, \cdot) \circ \varphi^{t_1}(t_0, \cdot) \quad \forall t_0 \leq t_1 \leq t_2 \in \mathcal{T} \quad (12)$$

for all $x : X, t_0, t_1, t_2 : \mathcal{T}$ such that both sides of the equations are defined when applied to x (and where id is the identity function on X).

Not all systems of PDEs or ODEs specify a dynamical system. But if for any initial time t_0 and initial state function $x_{x_0} : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow X$ there is a unique solution x_{x_0} for Eq. 4 such that for all $r : \mathbb{R}^d$

$$x_{x_0}(t_0, r) = x_0(r) \quad (13)$$

then a nonautonomous dynamical system $(\mathcal{T}, \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow X, \{\varphi^t\}_{t:\mathcal{T}})$ can be derived by defining

$$\varphi^t(t_0, x_0)(r) = x(t_0 + t, \cdot) = x_0(r) + \int_{t_0}^{t_0+t} \mathcal{F}(p, x)(\tau, r) d\tau. \quad (14)$$

To represent different kinds of non-determinism in dynamical systems, we use the abstract notion of *monad* [Mac78], following Ionescu [Ion09]. This approach leads to the notion of *monadic dynamical system*. Extending the above notion of nonautonomous dynamical system we define:

Nonautonomous Monadic Dynamical System

A *nonautonomous monadic dynamical system* is a quadruple $(\mathbf{M}, \mathcal{T}, X, \{\varphi_{\mathbf{M}}^t\}_{t:\mathcal{T}})$, where $\mathbf{M} = (M, \mu, \eta)$ is a monad, X is a state space, and $\{\varphi_{\mathbf{M}}^t : \mathcal{T} \times X \rightarrow M(X)\}_{t:\mathcal{T}}$ is a family of evolution operators satisfying the following properties:

$$\varphi_{\mathbf{M}}^0(t_0, \cdot) = \eta_X \quad \forall t_0 \in \mathcal{T} \quad (15)$$

$$\varphi_{\mathbf{M}}^{t_2}(t_0, \cdot) = \varphi^{t_2}(t_1, \cdot) \circ_{\mathbf{M}} \varphi_{\mathbf{M}}^{t_1}(t_0, \cdot) \quad \forall t_0 \leq t_1 \leq t_2 \in \mathcal{T} \quad (16)$$

where $\circ_{\mathbf{M}}$ denotes the composition of the Kleisli category of the monad \mathbf{M} .

The (families of) operations associated with a monad $\mathbf{M} = (M, \mu, \eta)$ have the signatures (for any type A)

$$\mu_A : M(M(A)) \rightarrow M(A)$$

$$\eta_A : M(M(A)) \rightarrow M(A)$$

We see that M is an operation that maps types into types:

$$M : Type \rightarrow Type$$

Moreover M needs to be a *functor* which means that there is for any types A, B an operation

$$map_{A,B} : (A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow (M(A) \rightarrow M(B))$$

that lifts functions into the monad. Subscripts for these functions are usually left implicit. Examples of monad functors are the powerset functor \mathcal{P} and the list functor *List* which can be used to model non-determinism, or a functor *Prob* of probability distributions⁷. The identity functor *Id* is also a monad and allows to recover deterministic dynamical systems from monadic ones.

⁷there are monads both for discrete and continuous probability distributions [Gir81; EK06; Jac15]

Example 5. The operations associated with the list monad are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{map}_{A,B} &: (A \rightarrow B) \rightarrow (\text{List}(A) \rightarrow \text{List}(B)) \\ \text{map}_{A,B}(f)([]) &= []_B \\ \text{map}_{A,B}(f)(a ::_A as) &= (f(a) ::_B \text{map}_{A,B}(f)(as)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_A &: A \rightarrow \text{List}(A) \\ \eta_A(a) &= [a]_A \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_A &: \text{List}(\text{List}(A)) \rightarrow \text{List}(A) \\ \mu_A([[]_A]_{\text{List}(A)}) &= []_A \\ \mu_A((as ::_{\text{List}(A)} ass)) &= as ++_A \mu_A(ass) \end{aligned}$$

where $[]_A : \text{List}(A)$ and $(::)_A : A \times \text{List}(A) \rightarrow \text{List}(A)$ are the *constructors* of the list type, $(++)_A : \text{List}(A) \times \text{List}(A) \rightarrow \text{List}(A)$ is the operation that appends two lists and $[a]_A$ is a notation for $(a ::_A [])$. The binary operations $(::)$ and $++$ are written infix.

When we subsequently use lists, subscripts will be dropped if they can be inferred from the context.

Time \mathcal{T} and time series

- The time set of a dynamical system can be \mathbb{R} (for *continuous* dynamical systems), \mathbb{Z}, \mathbb{N} (for *discrete* dynamical systems) or more generally a non-empty set that at least carries the structure of a monoid [Kuz13; GM12].
- *Time* in physical models is *continuous*, i.e. $\mathcal{T} = \mathbb{R}$.
- The index set \mathcal{I} of any sequence of observations (in their original form) is necessarily discrete and finite, corresponding to an index type $\mathcal{I} = \mathbb{N}_{<n}$ for some $n : \mathbb{N}$. To obtain a continuous sequence of data from observations of type D , a function $\mathbb{R} \rightarrow D$ has to be reconstructed from the given data points.
- A time series is called *regular* if no value is missing and values are equally spaced in time [Dak+12].
- Sequences of proxy data are typically not equally spaced, in the sense that the time spans between subsequent data points might vary. To make time series of observations from different sources comparable, sequences have to undergo a *dating* process to obtain a regular time series (see Ch.5.3.2 of [Goo15] for different dating methods).
- Computer simulations require some form of discretisation.

To bridge from the mathematical definition of a model and a continuous dynamical system to a computational framework, we need methods to obtain a discrete-time dynamical system that can approximate the dynamics described by a model or continuous-time system. Moreover such a computational framework should be flexible enough to vary model parameters and forcings. We do not dwell on discretisation or numerical methods in this report, we just note that given appropriate such methods, we can derive a discrete dynamical system roughly as follows:

Given a model with associated flow φ and a (finite)⁸ time discretisation $ts : \mathbb{N}_{\leq N} \rightarrow \mathcal{T}, N : \mathbb{N}, N > 0$, we can define a one step function

$$\begin{aligned} \text{next} &: \mathbb{N}_{<N} \times X \rightarrow X \\ \text{next}(k, x) &= \varphi^{ts(k+1)-ts(k)}(ts(k), x) \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

⁸One might alternatively want to determine a time step for arbitrary many steps via a function $\mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathcal{T}$, which would allow to compute simulations without fixing the number of computation steps in advance until a termination criterion is met. Such computations are not in general guaranteed to terminate and we do not discuss them further in this document.

and its iteration

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{flow} &: \mathbb{N}_{<N} \times X \rightarrow X \\
\text{flow}(0, x_0) &= x_0 \\
\text{flow}(n+1, x_0) &= \text{next}(n, \text{flow}(n, x_0))
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

to approximate φ on the interval $[ts(0), ts(N)]$ and compute trajectories by

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{trajectory} &: \mathbb{N}_{<N} \times X \rightarrow \text{List}(X) \\
\text{trajectory}(0, x_0) &= [x_0] \\
\text{trajectory}(n+1, x_0) &= \tau ++ [\text{next}(n, \text{last}(\tau))] \\
&\text{where } \tau = \text{trajectory}(n, x_0)
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

where $++$ appends lists and last returns the last element of a list.

Similar operations can be derived for a monadic dynamical system with flow $\varphi_{\mathbf{M}}$ for $\mathbf{M} = (M, \mu, \eta)$, using the monad's unit η and the functorial map of the underlying functor M .

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{next}_{\mathbf{M}} &: \mathbb{N}_{<N} \times X \rightarrow M(X) \\
\text{next}_{\mathbf{M}}(k, x) &= \varphi_{\mathbf{M}}^{ts(k+1)-ts(k)}(ts(k), x)
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{flow}_{\mathbf{M}} &: \mathbb{N}_{<N} \times X \rightarrow M(X) \\
\text{flow}_{\mathbf{M}}(0, x_0) &= \eta_X(x_0) \\
\text{flow}_{\mathbf{M}}(n+1, x_0) &= \text{map}(\lambda x. \text{next}(n, x))(\text{flow}(n, x_0))
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{trajectory}_{\mathbf{M}} &: \mathbb{N}_{<N} \times X \rightarrow M(\text{List}(X)) \\
\text{trajectory}_{\mathbf{M}}(0, x_0) &= \eta_{\text{List}(X)}([x_0]) \\
\text{trajectory}_{\mathbf{M}}(n+1, x_0) &= \text{map}(\lambda xs. xs ++ [\text{next}(n, \text{last}(xs))])(m\tau) \\
&\text{where } m\tau = \text{trajectory}_{\mathbf{M}}(n, x_0)
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

such that $(\mathbf{M}, \mathbb{N}, X, \{\text{flow}^{\mathbf{M}}(n, \cdot, \cdot)\}_{n:\mathbb{N}})$ is a discrete monadic dynamical system.

For numerical simulations, the deterministic *trajectory* function allows us to compute n -step approximations $[x_0, \dots, x_n] : \text{List}(X)$.⁹ Similarly, the monadic version of $\text{trajectory}_{\mathbf{M}}$ computes monadic values $mxs : M(\text{List}(X))$ containing such n -step trajectories. E.g. for a probability monad one would thus obtain a probability distribution of trajectories, and for the power set monad a set of trajectories.

In the following sections we discuss the key notions listed in the introduction using the framework introduced above.

4 Climate Sensitivity

Climate Sensitivity (CS) is a measure of the change of the *global mean surface temperature (GMST)* in response to the change of the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere. The first estimates have been published as early as 1896 [Arr96].

Since the 1960s scientists have been systematically studying the GMST change in response to the change of CO₂ content in the atmosphere along what is referred to as different lines of evidence [KRH17], combining model simulations with models of different levels of complexity with instrumental or paleoclimatic proxy data.

The classic *equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS)* experiment estimates the change in GMST relative to a reference state when the climate system will have settled to a new equilibrium after having been perturbed by doubling the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere.

⁹One might additionally want to indicate the order of the approximation, e.g. for a 0-dimensional model with solution $x : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow X$, a q -order approximation would guarantee that $x_k = x(t_k) + \mathcal{O}((\Delta t)^q)$ for a step length of $\Delta t : \mathcal{T}$.

Climate sensitivity, defined as a change in temperature measured between two equilibrium states, is and will remain a theoretical construction. The explicit measure of the temperature change at equilibrium cannot be made, in practice or in principle, because it would require “fixing” both external factors (i.e., the orbital forcing) and even internal components of the climate system (e.g., the “ice sheets”) and controlling accurately the CO₂ concentration.

Such experiments can however be made with climate models (simple and more complex), and it is our understanding of the connection between these models and the real world that allows us to attribute and estimate a “climate sensitivity” of our Earth. The meaning and intuition about climate sensitivity as a change in “equilibrium” states generally involves assumptions of time scale separation: climate sensitivity is understood as the measured response of some “fast” components of the climate system (e.g., the atmosphere) assuming that other components of the climate system have not changed (e.g., the ice sheets). As we will develop below, different assumptions about what is “fast” and “slow” lead to different definitions of the climate sensitivity, and [Roh+12] introduces a notation to that end.

The time scale separation is an arguable assumption (e.g., the adjustment time scale for the deep ocean temperature is of the order of 5000 years, a time scale over which the orbital forcing is significantly changed). Definitions of climate sensitivity that do not necessitate time scale separation have been proposed (e.g., [Ghi14] defines it as the growth of the Wasserstein distance between two pullback attractors) but their meaning is arguably much less intuitive.

Definitions. In the IPCC assessment reports, *equilibrium climate sensitivity* is defined as the change of GMST for the radiative forcing resulting from a doubling of the CO₂ level in the atmosphere wrt pre-industrial¹⁰, a temperature difference (see p. TS-14, [Mas+21]).

Another approach to ECS is based on an *equilibrium climate sensitivity parameter* [Roh+12] which quantifies a change in GMST per unit change in radiative forcing.

Equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS)

ECS: The *ECS* quantifies the change of GMST for the radiative forcing resulting from an intervention which doubles the CO₂ level in the atmosphere wrt preindustrial

$$\Delta T_{2\times\text{CO}_2} = T_{\text{eq}} - T_{\text{pi}} \quad \Delta T_{2\times\text{CO}_2}, T_{\text{eq}}, T_{\text{pi}} : \mathbb{R} \quad [\Delta T_{2\times\text{CO}_2}] = [T_{\text{eq}}] = [T_{\text{pi}}] = \Theta$$

where T_{pi} is the GMST at the preindustrial reference state and T_{eq} the equilibrium GMST reached when the system has returned to radiative equilibrium after the intervention.

ECS Parameter: The *ECS parameter* S_{\bullet} quantifies the change in mean surface temperature per unit change in radiative forcing

$$S_{\bullet} : \mathbb{R} \quad [S_{\bullet}] = \Theta \text{M}^{-1} \text{T}^3.$$

According to [Roh+12], it is typically assumed that $\Delta T_{2\times\text{CO}_2}$ is related to S_{\bullet} by

$$\Delta T_{2\times\text{CO}_2} = S_{\bullet} * \Delta Q_{2\times\text{CO}_2} \tag{23}$$

where $\Delta Q_{2\times\text{CO}_2} : \mathbb{R}, [\Delta Q_{2\times\text{CO}_2}] = \text{MT}^{-3}$ is the difference between the amount of radiative forcing resulting from a doubling of the CO₂ level in the atmosphere and a reference value prior to the doubling intervention.

According to Goosse [Goo15] “relatively good approximations” of the change in radiative forcing resulting from a change in CO₂ concentration “can be obtained [...] from a simple formula”. Myhre et al. [Myh+98] give the following formula¹¹:

$$\Delta Q_{\text{CO}_2} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad \Delta Q_{\text{CO}_2}(C, C_{\text{ref}}) = 5.35 * \ln\left(\frac{C}{C_{\text{ref}}}\right) \text{W m}^{-2} \tag{24}$$

¹⁰since the pre-industrial state is assumed to be in radiative equilibrium

¹¹Myhre et al. [Myh+98] also give formulas for other greenhouse gases, e.g. CH₄ and N₂O.

where $C, C_{\text{ref}} : \mathbb{R}$ are CO_2 concentrations of the atmosphere (dimensionless), for the current and a reference state, respectively, and $[\Delta Q_{\text{CO}_2}(C, C_{\text{ref}})] = \text{MT}^{-3}$. Using this formula, a doubling of the CO_2 concentration of the atmosphere results in a change of radiative forcing of $5.36 * \ln 2 \approx 3.7 \text{W m}^{-2}$.

The informal definitions given above suggest the following formalisation:

Let the evolution of the climate system with state space X be described by the flow $\{\varphi^t : X \rightarrow X\}_{t \in \mathcal{T}}$ and $x_{\text{pi}} : X$ be the pre-industrial state of the climate. Let moreover $\text{double} : X \rightarrow X$ be a function that doubles the CO_2 content of the atmosphere and $\text{gmst}, C_{\text{CO}_2} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be functions that compute the GMST and the CO_2 concentration in the atmosphere, respectively. Then

$$\Delta T_{2 \times \text{CO}_2} = T_{\text{eq}} - T_{\text{pi}}$$

where

$$T_{\text{eq}} = \text{gmst} \left(\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varphi^t(\text{double}(x_{\text{pi}})) \right) \quad \text{and} \quad T_{\text{pi}} = \text{gmst}(x_{\text{pi}})$$

and, if S_{\bullet} is defined based on $\Delta T_{2 \times \text{CO}_2}$,

$$S_{\bullet} = \frac{\Delta T_{2 \times \text{CO}_2}}{\Delta Q_{2 \times \text{CO}_2}} \approx 0.3 * \Delta T_{2 \times \text{CO}_2}$$

$$\text{where} \quad \Delta Q_{2 \times \text{CO}_2} = \Delta Q_{\text{CO}_2}(C_{\text{CO}_2}(\text{double}(x_{\text{pi}})), C_{\text{CO}_2}(x_{\text{pi}})) \approx 3.7 \text{W m}^{-2}$$

ECS as a standard metric for climate models is however more specific with respect to the processes that are modelled (see [below](#)). One might also want to represent internal variability of the climate system or uncertainty about the pre-industrial climate state by using a stochastic model.

Radiation balance. The relation between $\Delta T_{2 \times \text{CO}_2}$ and S_{\bullet} given in Eq. (23) follows from the idea [Goo15; Han+84] that, given a particular change in radiative forcing $\Delta Q : \mathbb{R}$, the radiative balance (the difference between incoming and outgoing radiation at the top of the atmosphere) $\Delta R(x) : \mathbb{R}, [\Delta R(x)] = \text{MT}^{-3}$ for a climate state $x : X$ can be estimated by a linear function $\tilde{R} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with

$$\tilde{R}(\Delta T(x)) = \Delta Q - \frac{1}{S_{\bullet}} * \Delta T(x) \tag{25}$$

which takes a temperature difference $\Delta T(x) = \text{gmst}(x) - \text{gmst}(x_{\text{ref}})$ between the climate state and a reference state $x_{\text{ref}} : X$ as input.

The system is in radiative equilibrium in state x if $\Delta R(x) = 0$. This is the case if

$$\Delta T(x) = \Delta Q * S_{\bullet} \tag{26}$$

Doing this calculation for $\Delta Q_{2 \times \text{CO}_2}$, we get (an estimation of) $\Delta T_{2 \times \text{CO}_2}$ as in Eq. (23) above.

On the other hand, if $\Delta Q_{2 \times \text{CO}_2}$ and $\Delta T_{2 \times \text{CO}_2}$ have been determined by a numerical simulation, Eq. 26 can be used to calculate (an estimation of) a value for S_{\bullet} .

The negated inverse of the ECS parameter, $-S_{\bullet}^{-1}$ (the slope of \tilde{R} above) is called the *climate feedback*. It can in turn be understood as being the sum of multiple different feedbacks (see [below](#)).

Variants. Estimates of ECS based on different data sources vary. Reasons for these differences are recently being addressed in the literature, and also other variants of climate sensitivity have been proposed. The IPCC lists the following variants of climate sensitivity:

Climate Sensitivity: Variants

- *equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS)*
- *effective climate sensitivity (EECS)*

- *earth system sensitivity (ESS)*
- *transient climate response (TCR)*
- *transient climate response to cumulative CO₂ emissions (TCRE)*

Using the notion of radiative forcing, the IPCC calls different variants of climate sensitivity *climate metrics*: ”Measures of aspects of the overall climate system response to radiative forcing” [Mat+21]. Given the IPCC definition of *ECS* as response to a change in the CO₂ concentration, this definition of *climate metric* seems to implicitly translate a change in CO₂ concentration into an estimation of corresponding radiative forcing.

We will address the differences between these variants in Section 4.1 below.

Estimation methods. Knutti et al. [KRH17] write about different ways of estimating climate sensitivity (and give an extensive overview over different estimates in the literature in their figures 1–3):

“ECS and TCR cannot be measured directly, but in principle they can be estimated from:

- quantifying feedbacks, ECS and TCR in comprehensive climate models;
- potentially constraining models by their representation of present-day mean climate and variability;
- analysis of the post-industrial observed warming of the ocean and atmosphere in response to forcing
- the short-term climate response to forcing (such as volcanic eruptions) or interannual temperature variations;
- paleoclimate records (for example, the cooling at the Last Glacial Maximum or the warming during earlier warm periods). ”

The authors of [Roh+12] emphasise that in order to make estimates of climate sensitivity comparable, it is important to be transparent about the *climate feedbacks* a particular calculation accounts for. Knutti and Rugenstein illustrate which feedbacks are typically included in the different variants of *CS*, on which time scales these feedbacks occur (in Fig. 1(b) and Fig. 2, respectively, of [KR15]) and also indicate which time scales relate to which kind of data (model simulation output, instrumental and proxy records). However, they also remark:

”The separation of ECS and ESS is often made along timescales, with the argument that those feedbacks included in ECS essentially scale with surface temperature, whereas others in ESS partly have their intrinsic (and often slower) timescales. However, this does not apply to atmospheric chemistry which responds quickly. Here, the reason is a historic one, as the early climate models simply did not simulate interactive chemistry. This supports the argument that the separation of ECS and ESS is somewhat arbitrary in the real world where a lot of processes interact.”

Climate feedbacks: Examples

The estimations of climate sensitivity differ in terms of the climate feedbacks taken into account

- *ECS, TCR, TCRE* include the following up to centennial scale (“fast”) feedbacks:
 - clouds
 - lapse rate
 - water vapour

Figure 2: Example of positive and negative feedback loops. (Redrawn from TiPES Deliverable D4.1)

- albedo/land surface
- Planck
- *ESS*: Additionally included feedback processes:
 - atmospheric chemistry (another “fast” feedback that however was not available in earlier generations of process-based models)
 - up to millennia or longer (“slow”):
 - * ocean circulation, ocean chemistry, weathering
 - * dynamic vegetation, terrestrial ecosystems
 - * permafrost carbon
 - * ice sheets

Which of these feedbacks contribute to the calculation of a particular variant of CS is determined by the model that is being used. The ECS parameter can be refined by considering a sum of feedback parameters

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \quad \lambda_i : \mathbb{R} \quad [\lambda_i] = \Theta^{-1} \text{MT}^{-3} \quad 1 \leq i \leq n : \mathbb{N} \quad (27)$$

and defining the ECS parameter as (cf. [KR15; Roh+12])

$$S_{\bullet} = -\frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i}. \quad (28)$$

4.1 Computational structure of CS experiments

We have to distinguish between simple EBMs in which climate sensitivity is included as a parameter (or based on a small number of feedback parameters) and more complex models in which climate sensitivity is an “emergent property” and measured as response to perturbation of the system.

As seen above, different methods to estimate climate sensitivity are used in the literature. Here we describe two representative ones:

1. performing a perturbation experiment with a complex climate model to observe the resulting change in temperature (as emergent behaviour);
2. given observation or proxy data for a reference period, use a simple model which is parameterised over S_{\bullet} , perform model simulations for that reference period using different plausible values S_{\bullet} , and compare the model output to the given data to see which choice of the parameter fits best according to a chosen measure.

Estimation by perturbation experiment. The first approach consists in a perturbation experiment with a complex model in which climate sensitivity is an emergent property. We describe this method in parallel for the different variants of CS.

Given:

- A model m with time set \mathcal{T} , state space X , parameters $(f, p') : (\mathcal{T} \rightarrow P) \times P'$, where the first component denotes a potentially time-dependent forcing, and a dynamical system induced by the model.
- An initial state $x_0 : X$ at time $t_0 : \mathcal{T}$, often a preindustrial state, in (near) radiative equilibrium or, a probability distribution on initial states $px_0 : Prob(X)$
- A perturbed initial state $x'_0 : X$, for example obtained by doubling the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere of the initial state through a function $double : X \rightarrow X$, with $x'_0 = double(x_0)$ and $px'_0 = map(double)(px_0) : Prob(List(X))$ in the probabilistic case.

Now the basic computation follows the scheme of what we might call a *comparison experiment*:

- Compute two numerical approximations for a time discretisation Δt

$$xs_{\text{ref}} = [x_0, \dots, x_n] = trajectory(n, x_0) \text{ and } xs = [x'_0, \dots, x'_n] = trajectory(n, x'_0)$$

in the deterministic case or otherwise two probability distributions $pxs, pxs' : Prob(List(X))$ either by

$$pxs_{\text{ref}} = trajectory_{Prob}(n, x_0) \quad pxs = trajectory_{Prob}(n, x'_0)$$

or

$$pxs_{\text{ref}} = map(trajectory(n, \cdot))(px_0) \quad pxs = map(trajectory(n, \cdot))(px'_0)$$

xs_{ref} and pxs_{ref} play the role of reference trajectory and reference distribution of trajectories, respectively.

- Compare xs_{ref} and xs or pxs_{ref} and pxs , respectively, using functions

$$compare_{\text{det}} : List(X)^2 \rightarrow Val_c$$

or

$$compare_{\text{prob}} : Prob(List(X))^2 \rightarrow Val_c$$

where Val_c is a type of values, e.g. \mathbb{R} .

This comparison might for example be done in terms of the difference between the global mean surface temperature at statistically measured end states $x_f, x_{f_{\text{ref}}} : X$ ¹² obtained by applying a function

$$measureX : List(X) \rightarrow X$$

¹²Again, if we assume some form of time scale separation, the “statistical measure” involves that states x_f and x_{ref} are observed over a time long enough to effectively sample the fluctuations of the fast variables. In technical terms, we want to measure the invariant set of meteorological variables associated with the climate states x_f . Discarding this time-scale separation assumption comes at a huge cost: it involves introducing the notion of *pullback attractor* (e.g. [Ghi14]) that would be overwhelming for our purpose.

to xs and xs_{ref} :

$$gmst(x_f) - gmst(x_{f_{\text{ref}}}) \quad \text{where} \quad x_f = \text{measure}X(xs), \quad x_{f_{\text{ref}}} = \text{measure}X(xs_{\text{ref}}).$$

See below for remarks concerning different algorithmic possibilities for the comparison of trajectories.

The different variants of climate sensitivity now correspond to variations in the models and different ways of computing the numerical approximations (we just give the deterministic variants, the probabilistic/monadic ones can be obtained as above using *map*):

- – *ECS*: Choose a model m_{ECS} that represents the processes required to account for the climate feedbacks usually associated with ECS and a forcing

$$Const_{\text{CO}_2} : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

that keeps the atmospheric concentration of CO_2 constant. Perturb initial state by doubling the CO_2 concentration and integrate the model maintaining this perturbation until an/a (approximate/statistical) radiative equilibrium state is reached after $n_{ECS} : \mathbb{N}$ steps

The computation thus amounts to

$$xs = (\text{trajectory}_{m_{ECS}}(n_{ECS}, \cdot) \circ \text{double})(x_0)$$

For the reference path integrate the model with the unperturbed initial state.

$$xs_{\text{ref}} = \text{trajectory}_{m_{ECS}}(n_{ECS}, \cdot)(x_0)$$

Then $\Delta T_{2 \times \text{CO}_2}$ can be computed as indicated above by comparing the global mean surface temperature for the representative final states resulting from these two computations.

- *ESS*: As for ECS but with a model m_{ESS} that accounts for all the feedbacks to be considered for ESS and a number of computation steps $n_{ESS} : \mathbb{N}$ such that all processes can (approximately) equilibrate.
- *EECS*: Use a model m_{ECS} as for ECS. Perturb the initial state and integrate the model for $n_{EECS} : \mathbb{N}$ time steps representing $\approx 100 - 200$ yrs. Then estimate an equilibrium state $x_{\text{eq}} : X$ using a function $\text{estimate}_{\text{eq}} : \text{List}(X) \rightarrow X$ ¹³

$$x_{\text{eq}} = (\text{estimate}_{\text{eq}} \circ \text{trajectory}_{m_{ECS}}(n_{EECS}, \cdot) \circ \text{double})(x_0)$$

Do the same with the unperturbed initial state to obtain a reference equilibrium state $x_{\text{ref-eq}}$. Compute the difference in GMST between the two equilibrium states as above.

- *TCR*: Use a model m_{TCR} with a forcing

$$Inc_{1\% \text{CO}_2} : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

representing a 1% increase of atmospheric CO_2 concentration per year until the double of the initial CO_2 concentration is reached.¹⁴ (Again, the forcing is given as part of the model parameters, say $p = (Inc_{1\% \text{CO}_2}, p')$ where p' might be other parameters.) Integrate the model for $n_{TCR} : \mathbb{N}$ time steps, representing $\approx 60 - 80$ yrs. Then compute a representative climate state by averaging globally in space, and over 20 yrs in time, centred at the time of CO_2 doubling, using a function $\text{climate} : \text{List}(X) \rightarrow X$

$$x_f = (\text{climate} \circ \text{trajectory}_{m_{TCR}}(n_{TCR}, \cdot))(x_0)$$

Compute the GMST difference between x_f and a reference state.

¹³standard methods applied in studies cited by the IPCC are from [Han+05] – using fixed sea surface temperatures – and [Gre+04] – using linear regression

¹⁴This seems to require knowledge about the *CO* concentration for the initial state to define the forcing.

For a given dynamical system with state space X and a numerical method for computing $N : \mathbb{N}$ time steps, we suggest the following generic schemes:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{comparisonExperiment} &: (\text{List}(X)^2 \rightarrow \text{Val}_c) \times \mathbb{N}_{<N} \times X^2 \rightarrow \text{Val}_c \\ \text{comparisonExperiment}(\text{compare}, n, x, x') & \\ &= (\text{compare} \circ \text{map}(\text{trajectory}(n, \cdot)))(x, x') \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{perturbExperiment} &: (\text{List}(X)^2 \rightarrow \text{Val}_c) \times (X \rightarrow X) \times \mathbb{N}_{<N} \times X \rightarrow \text{Val}_c \\ \text{perturbExperiment}(\text{compare}, \text{perturb}, n, x) & \\ &= \text{comparisonExperiment}(\text{compare}, n, x, \text{perturb}(x)) \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Based on these, one might describe a general CO₂ doubling CS experiment as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{csExperiment} &: \mathbb{N}_{<N} \times X \rightarrow \text{Val}_c \\ \text{csExperiment}(n, x) &= \text{perturbExperiment}(\text{gmst} \circ \text{measure}X, \text{double}, n, x) \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

When such simulations are performed with multiple models, the results might in the simplest case be averaged. However, one might also incorporate information from model validations: the better a model is capable of reproducing observational data for a reference time period, the more credible it is. When aggregating CS values resulting from the same experiment with different models (as in the CMIP project), the individual values might thus be weighted according to the performance of the respective model in validation experiments.

Parameter experiment. The idea of validating the model output against reference data also forms the basis for the second method, yet in a different way.

This time, CS is not estimated as an emergent property of the model, but included in the model as a parameter.

This time we have

- A list of candidate values for the ECS parameter $cs = [S_0, \dots, S_k]$.
- A list of models $[m_0, \dots, m_k]$ with state space X and parameter space $P = \mathbb{R} \times P'$, where the first component of a parameter fixes the value of the ECS parameter such that model m_i has parameters (S_i, p') for $0 \leq i \leq k$.
- A time series $o : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \text{Val}_o$ of observational data and a time discretisation $[t_0, \dots, t_n]$ for an interval of interest.
- An initial state $x_0 : X$ compatible with the observations $o(t_0)$

With these inputs:

- Compute numerical approximations

$$xs_i = [x_{i0}, \dots, x_{in}] = \text{trajectory}_{m_i}(n, x_0) \quad (0 \leq i \leq k)$$

for the different candidate values of the ECS parameter.

- Extract the observations of interest from the states in each xs_i via by mapping an observation function $\text{observe} : X \rightarrow \text{Val}_o$

$$oxs_i = \text{map}(\text{observe})(xs_i)$$

and compare the oxs_i to the observational reference data $os = [o(t_0), \dots, o(t_n)]$ according to a distance metric $\text{compare} : \text{List}(\text{Val}_o)^2 \rightarrow \text{Val}_c$, resulting in a list of distances $[d_0, \dots, d_k]$ where $d_i = \text{compare}(oxs_i, os)$.

- Determine which of the xs_i is the best approximation to the observational data using a function $best : (ds : List(\mathbb{R})) \rightarrow \mathbb{N}_{<length(ds)}$ which returns the index j of the best approximation.
- Return the candidate value for the ECS parameter that best fits the given observations os :¹⁵

$$S_{best} = nth(cs, best(map(compare \circ map(observe))([xs_0, \dots, xs_k])))$$

where the auxiliary function $nth : (l : List(A)) \times \mathbb{N}_{<length(l)} \rightarrow A$ given a list and an index (smaller than the length of the list) returns the list element at that index.

Remarks. Above we did not address algorithmic particularities of *how* to compare trajectories. In fact, there are structurally different ways to proceed.

Given an observable

$$observe : X \rightarrow Val_o,$$

a comparison function

$$compare : Val_o^2 \rightarrow Val_c,$$

and an aggregation function for Val_c ¹⁶

$$aggregateVal_c : List(Val_c) \rightarrow Val_c$$

one could first compute a point-wise comparison between the two trajectories and then aggregate the outcomes:^{17 18}

$$(aggregateVal_c \circ map^{List}(compare))(zip(map^\blacktriangle(map^{List}(observe))(xs, xs')))$$

spelled out: given a pair of trajectories $(xs, xs') : List(X)^2$, the function $observe$ is mapped onto each of the two trajectories using map^{List} and map^\blacktriangle . This results in a pair of two lists of observations ($List(Val_o)^2$) which are “zipped” together resulting in a list of pairs of observations ($List(Val_o^2)$). Then the function $compare$ is mapped onto this list of observation pairs, again using map^{List} . The resulting list of comparison values ($List(Val_c)$) is finally aggregated to a single outcome of type Val_c .¹⁹

Alternatively, given an aggregation function

$$aggregateVal_o : List(Val_o) \rightarrow Val_o$$

one may first aggregate the state observations and then compare the results:

$$(compare \circ map^\blacktriangle(aggregateVal_o \circ map^{List}(observe)))(xs, xs')$$

The two options will not necessarily give the same results.

For the probabilistic case (and similar for an arbitrary monad), additionally a measure

$$measureVal_o : Prob(Val_o) \rightarrow Val_o,$$

or

$$measureVal_c : Prob(Val_c) \rightarrow Val_c$$

¹⁵Mapping a function f onto a list $[x_0, \dots, x_n]$ means applying this function to each element of the list without changing the order of the elements, i.e. $map(f)([x_0, \dots, x_n]) = [f(x_0), \dots, f(x_n)]$.

¹⁶which in turn might be induced by a binary operation $\oplus : Val_c^2 \rightarrow Val_c$

¹⁷Below we annotate the map function for the different functors for better readability. We write map^\blacktriangle for the map of the diagonal functor $Diag : Type \rightarrow Type$ with $Diag(A) = A \times A$, map^{List} for the map of the list functor defined in Example 5 and map^{Prob} for the map of a functor that maps each type to the type of probability distributions over this type.

¹⁸The function $zip : List(A) \times List(B) \rightarrow List(A \times B)$ transforms a pair of lists of equal lengths into a list of pairs of the same length: $zip([a_0, \dots, a_n], [b_0, \dots, b_n]) = [(a_0, b_0), \dots, (a_n, b_n)]$.

¹⁹For reading long concatenations of multiple functions, proceed from right to left and trace the types of the intermediate computations.

is required to compute an outcome of type Val_c .²⁰

Now, two probability distributions of trajectories $pxs, pxs' : Prob(List(X))$ can e.g. be compared by

$$(compare \circ map^\blacktriangleleft (measureVal_o \circ map^{Prob}(aggregateVal_o \circ map^{List}(observe))))(pxs, pxs')$$

or

$$measureVal_c \circ map^{Prob}(compare) \circ map^\blacktriangleleft (map^{Prob}(aggregateVal_o \circ map^{List}(observe)))(pxs, pxs')$$

Again, it is not clear that these computations will return the same result.

It would also be interesting to consider non-deterministic variants of the second experiment. Moreover, one might want to compute not only one optimal solution but several that are “good enough” according to some metric and compare the corresponding choices for S_\bullet .

IPCC estimates. Using such and other methods, the IPCC gives estimates of value ranges for $\Delta T_{2 \times CO_2}$ based on “Understanding of climate processes, the instrumental record, paleoclimates and model-based emergent constraints”. According to the AR6 WGI report, it is considered as *very likely*²¹ that the value of $\Delta T_{2 \times CO_2}$ lies between 2°C and 5°C with *high confidence* in the lower and *medium confidence* in the upper bound. As best estimate the report now gives a value of 3°C with [2.5°C, 4°C] as *high confidence* range, while in AR5 a best estimate was not given and the *likely* range was stated as [1.5°C, 4.5°C]. (However, it is also said that the CMIP6 models exhibit “a larger range of climate sensitivity” and a higher average than the CMIP5 models and the AR6 best estimate. This behaviour is attributed to an amplifying cloud feedback.) Besides giving these ranges, the report also states that since AR5 “independent lines of evidence, including proxy records from past warm periods and glacial-interglacial cycles, indicate that sensitivity to forcing increases as temperature increases (TS.3.2.2)”. The latter seems to indicate that “sensitivity to forcing” is to be understood not with respect to pre-industrial as in the IPCC’s ECS definition, but in a more general sense in which reference states with different values of GMST can be considered.

4.2 Selected references

Origins and early studies:

- A very early study of the influence of the CO₂ content of the atmosphere on the mean surface temperature: Arrhenius [Arr96].
- Budyko [Bud69] and Sellers [Sel69] study EBM models of the radiative fluxes at the top of the atmosphere.
- The original definition of ECS stems from the *Charney report* [Cha+79] which also gave the first estimate range based on the models by Manabe/Wetherald [MW75] and Sellers [Sel69].
- Hansen et al. [Han+84] study climate sensitivity in three ways that have become standard “lines of evidence”: by model simulation, from paleo data and from the instrumental record.
- An early review of climate sensitivity studies: Schlesinger [Sch83].

There is a huge body of literature with computations of forms of ECS and TCR based on different lines of evidence. In the last decade there have been efforts to systematise these results and to develop the notion of “climate sensitivity” to be more specific about underlying assumptions of individual computations of climate sensitivity. As studies have also shown a likely state dependence of ECS (e.g. [AGW15]), recent publications suggest extensions to the basic concept. The latter is

²⁰Note that $aggregateVal_o$ and $aggregateVal_c$ might be seen as measures for the list monad.

²¹The IPCC uses a “calibrated language” for a consistent treatment of uncertainty estimates where natural language expressions like *likely*, *very likely*, *high confidence* are chosen according to guidelines described in [Mas+10].

the focus of TiPES WP4 “From Climate Sensitivity to a general theory of Climate Response across scales”.

The following are papers that systematise and improve the study of climate sensitivity and more generally the climate response to external forcing:

- The PALEOSENS group [Roh+12] is concerned with a systematic treatment of ECS studies based on paleo data. To generalise the standard $2\times\text{CO}_2$ ECS notion they propose to use a climate sensitivity parameter per unit radiative forcing instead (the parameter S_\bullet discussed above) and to make explicit the time-scale of the climate feedbacks that are considered in the sensitivity computation. Beyond the “Charney” definition of ECS which includes “fast” feedbacks, they propose ESS as a variant of ECS with the same general structure, but which also includes “slow” feedbacks.
- The authors of [Hey+16] study and discuss the problems with ECS in presence of tipping points.
- Knutti et al. discuss the shortcomings of linearity assumptions (as e.g. in Eq. 25) that are common in climate sensitivity studies in [KR15] and alternative metrics “beyond ECS” in [KRH17].
- A long recent report [She+20] on the assessment of “Earth’s climate sensitivity” combines evidence from the understanding of feedback processes and both the historical and the paleo record with expert judgement. To transparently deal with uncertainty, the *storyline* approach [She+18] is employed, as already done in an earlier paper by some of the authors [Ste+16]

A concluding quote on the difficulty of “quantifying ECS” from [She+20]:

Quantifying ECS is challenging because the available evidence consists of diverse strands, none of which is conclusive by itself. This requires that the strands be combined in some way. Yet, because the underlying science spans many disciplines within the Earth Sciences, individual scientists generally only fully understand one or a few of the strands. Moreover, the interpretation of each strand requires structural assumptions that cannot be proven, and sometimes ECS measures have been estimated from each strand that are not fully equivalent. This complexity and uncertainty thwarts rigorous, definitive calculations and gives expert judgement and assumptions a potentially large role.

5 Commitment

In the context of climate change, one comes across three different notions of *commitment*:

1. *climate change commitment* as a technical notion, used to quantify delayed responses of the climate system due to some form of inertia, e.g. warming that would result from past emissions even if CO_2 emissions were stopped immediately
2. *commitment* in the sense of contractual obligation as used in e.g. in the Kyoto protocol
3. *commitment* as a modal operator capturing a form of personal dedication to the fulfilment of a task

Our main focus here is on the first notion.

5.1 Climate change commitment

The first usage of this notion according to the AR4 WGI report is in [Ram88].

“The inferred trace gas increases from the preindustrial era to the present have *committed* the planet to an equilibrium surface warming of about 0.6 to 2.4 K. Furthermore, at the current rate of increase in the trace gases, the *committed equilibrium warming* of the globe increases by about 0.13 to 0.5 K per decade.” (*emphasis added*)

We see that Ramanathan’s notion of commitment is defined in terms of an *equilibrium warming*. Wetherald et al. [WSD01] similarly consider a notion of *warming commitment*:

“The difference between the realized warming at a given time and the warming of climate that would occur if the climate had an infinitely long time to adjust to that radiative forcing (i.e. the gap between the equilibrium and the realized temperature change for a given forcing) is referred to here as “the **warming commitment**”.

We re-examine the present day **warming commitment**, its future changes and other **committed climate responses**. [...] allows the **climatic commitment** of a wide range of variables to be examined [...]” (*emphasis as in the source*)

Wigley’s 2005 paper “The climate change commitment” [Wig05] (according to the IPCC AR5 WGI contribution) is the source of the terminology and most of the variants of the *climate change commitment* notion in the IPCC glossary. On alternative terminology for commitment in earlier work Wigley writes:

“For global-mean temperature, this is referred to as the unrealized warming [Han+85], residual warming [Wig84], or committed warming [WSD01]. Here, I use the term **warming commitment** or, to include sea level rise [WR93; SM99], **climate change commitment**.” (*citations adapted*)

and on *equilibrium warming commitment*:

“The **usual (or equilibrium) CC warming commitment at time t** is the **difference between the equilibrium warming for forcing at this time (ΔT_e) and the corresponding realized warming (ΔT_r), $\Delta T_e - \Delta T_r$** . This is related to the radiation-imbalance concept [Han+02; Pie03]. If ΔQ is the forcing to date, and if ΔQ_r is the forcing that gives an equilibrium warming of ΔT_r , then the radiation imbalance is $\Delta Q - \Delta Q_r$ ($\Delta Q - \Delta Q_r$ is approximately equal to the flux of heat into the ocean [Pie03]). Hence

$$\Delta T_e - \Delta T_r = (\Delta Q - \Delta Q_r)(\Delta T_{2\times} / \Delta Q_{2\times})$$

where $\Delta Q_{2\times}$ is the radiative forcing for a CO₂ doubling (about 3.7W m⁻²) and $\Delta T_{2\times}$ is the corresponding equilibrium global-mean warming. A central estimate of ΔQ (accounting for both natural and anthropogenic forcings) is about 1.7W m⁻², whereas ΔT_r is about 0.7°C. Given $\Delta T_{2\times} = 2.6^\circ\text{C}$ [WR01], a central value for the current **equilibrium warming commitment** is about 0.5°C, with a corresponding radiation-imbalance estimate of 0.7W m⁻². These results are in accord with other estimates in the literature, but uncertainties are large.” (*citations adapted*)

We see that the computation of equilibrium climate commitment presented by Wigley depends on the value of ECS. He motivates his above computation of equilibrium commitment by referring to “the radiation-imbalance concept”. To our understanding, he assumes the relation between change in radiative forcing and change in temperature discussed in the beginning of Section 4, such that $(\Delta T_{2\times} / \Delta Q_{2\times}) = 1/S_\bullet$. The estimate $\Delta Q_{2\times} \approx 3.7\text{W m}^{-2}$ coincides with the estimate resulting from the Myhre et al. formula of Eq. (24).

Wigley posits the two scenarios that are still standard:

“The assumption of constant atmospheric composition on which the warming commitment idea is based is clearly unrealistic, even as an extreme case of what might happen in the future. An alternative indicator of the **commitment to climate change** is to assume that the emissions (rather than concentrations) of radiatively important species will remain constant. This Report investigates the **constant-composition (CC) warming and sea level commitments**, the **constant-emissions (CE) commitments**, and the uncertainties in each.”

He proposes to study time-dependent variants of commitment instead of just the equilibrium/asymptotic commitment ²²

“ Because it would take an infinite time for the unrealized warming to appear, a more useful definition makes the unrealized warming a time-dependent quantity, namely, the evolving changes in global-mean temperature that would result if atmospheric composition were kept constant at its present state [Wig84]. This is the definition I use here. Temperatures under this new definition tend asymptotically to the previous equilibrium commitment definition. The new definition can be applied equally to the **CC and CE commitments** and can be used for both temperature and sea level.” (*citation adapted*)

Further geophysical variants. Wigley’s definitions of commitment are based on a difference, while the AR5 WGI report [Kri+13] also mentions the usage of a ratio-based constant composition commitment, citing [Sto04; Mee+07; Sol+09; Eby+09]:

“A measure of constant composition commitment is the fraction of realized warming which can be estimated as the ratio of the warming at a given time to the long-term equilibrium warming [...].”

Furthermore, the AR5 WGI report discusses the following form of commitment studied in [CC10] (and similarly in [Hel+10]):

“Another form of commitment refers to climate change associated with heat and carbon that has gone into the land surface and oceans. This would be relevant to the consequences of a one-time removal of all of the excess CO₂ in the atmosphere and is computed by taking a transient simulation and instantaneously setting atmospheric CO₂ concentrations to initial (pre-industrial) values [...].”

Non-geophysical variants. There are also notions of commitment that are related to inertia in technological, societal and economical aspects. An overview is given in the AR5 WGI report [Kri+13]:

“A **more general form of commitment** is the question of how much warming we are committed to as a result of inertia and hence commitments related to the time scales for energy system transitions and other societal, economic and technological aspects (Grubb, 1997; Washington et al., 2009; Davis et al., 2010). For example, Davis et al. (2010) estimated **climate commitment** of 1.3°C (range 1.1°C to 1.4°C, relative to pre-industrial) **from existing CO₂-emitting devices** under specific assumptions regarding their lifetimes. These forms of commitment, however, are strongly based on political, economic and social assumptions that are outside the domain of IPCC WGI and are not further considered here.”

5.2 Other usages

Commitment also denotes an obligation following from entering a contract. E.g. in the following paragraph from the IPCC AR5:

“[...] Parties with quantified emission limitations (and reduction obligations) in aggregate may have bettered their collective emission reduction target in the first *commitment* period, but some emissions reductions that would have occurred even in its absence were also counted. The Protocol’s Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) created a market for emissions offsets from developing countries, the purpose being two-fold: to help Annex I countries fulfill their *commitments* [...].” (*emphasis added*)

²²Apparently he has already used this approach in [Wig84] which he cites; this paper however seems to be unavailable online.

The above refers to the Kyoto protocol which has two *commitment periods*. The [European Commission Website](#) writes about the first commitment period:

“In the first period of the Protocol (2008-12), participating countries *committed to* reduce their emissions by an average of 5% below 1990 levels.” (*emphasis added*)

Of the non-technical meanings of *commit* and *commitment* listed in the *Oxford English Dictionary* item 6 seems to be closest to the usage in climate science:

“6. a. The action or an act of obligating or binding oneself or another to a particular course of action, policy, etc.; the action of giving an undertaking, either explicitly or by implication. Also: an undertaking or pledge of this kind.

[...]

b. An act or course of action to which a person is bound or obligated; an obligation, responsibility; a liability; an engagement.”

There is also recent game-theoretic work concerning a similar notion of *conditional commitment* [Hei19].

Deontic logic. Feltus and Petit [FP09] propose a formalisation of a commitment modality in standard deontic logic (a *modal logic* concerned with *obligation*, *permission* and related concepts). Their understanding of commitment is described as follows:

“It appears that this option proposition, even if optional to an organizational accountability, could remain engaged toward a moral obligation that we call **Commitment**. This commitment could be defined as the act of binding itself (intellectually or emotionally) to a course of actions.”

This seems more compatible with item 7 of the OED:

“7. a. The state or quality of being dedicated to a cause, ideology, activity, etc.; the action of devoting oneself to something or someone; devotion, dedication.”

5.3 Instances of climate change commitment

As we have seen, there are different instances of *climate change commitment*, depending on which forcing scenario is used, which feature of the climate system is of interest and whether an equilibrium or a transient version of the notion is considered.

Climate Change Commitment: Instances

- with respect to different features of a climate system:
 - temperature
 - in the hydrological cycle
 - extreme weather events
 - extreme climate events
 - sea level change
- with respect to specific scenarios:
 - constant composition
 - constant emission
 - zero emission
 - feasible scenario
- as transient or equilibrium notion

5.4 Computational structure of climate change commitment

Climate change commitment can be estimated similarly to climate sensitivity by model simulation, from:

- A model m with state space X and parameters $(f, p') : (\mathcal{T} \rightarrow P) \times P'$ where the first component denotes a forcing
- An initial time $t_0 : \mathcal{T}$ and state $x_0 : X$
- A numerical method for computing approximations $trajectory_m(n, x_0) = [x_0, \dots, x_n]$ for a time discretisation $[t_0, \dots, t_n]$
- a reference time $t_{ref} : \mathcal{T}$ and state $x_{ref} : X$ (in which the climate system is not necessarily in radiative equilibrium)
- a forcing $f : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

The main variants of climate change commitment assessments listed in the glossary of the IPCC's SR15 [IPC18] differ only in the considered forcings: *constant composition*, *constant emissions*, *zero emissions* and *feasible* scenario, defined as functions

$$\begin{aligned} constComposition &: \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ constEmissions &: \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ zeroEmissions &: \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ feasible &: \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \end{aligned}$$

which force the components of the system's state that represent the atmospheric concentration of CO₂ to

- remain constant
- change corresponding to a constant amount of anthropogenic emissions
- change according to zero anthropogenic emissions
- change according to the minimal amount of anthropogenic emissions that is judged as feasible

If another forcing scenario f is used, the idea that commitment quantifies the response of the climate system when an anthropogenic forcing is stopped or at least does not increase anymore suggests that f should be a non-increasing function:

$$\forall t, t' : \mathcal{T}, t < t' \Rightarrow f(t) \geq f(t')$$

- a function $observe : X \rightarrow Val_o$ observing the feature of a climate state we are interested in, e.g. again a function that computes the GMST as in Section 4 or a measure of the sea level

$$gmst : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$sealevel : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

- a function that aggregates a trajectory to a representative state (as in Section 4)

$$aggregateX : List(X) \rightarrow X$$

- and a comparison function $compareVal_o : Val_o^2 \rightarrow Val_c$ that allows us to compare the resulting values of the feature of interest. Typically Val_o and Val_c are numerical types and the comparison function computes the difference of two numbers or their ratio.

The computation then follows the structure of a comparison experiment. To our understanding the difference to the CS experiments described in Section 4 is that here the reference state which is used for comparison is not supposed to be in equilibrium.

We have seen above that Wigley distinguishes between transient and equilibrium commitment experiments. From a theoretical perspective, when integrating a dynamical system indefinitely “until an equilibrium is reached”, it is not guaranteed that it will ever do so and the computation terminate. In practice however, the computations performed for an equilibrium experiment will rather correspond to a transient experiment for a number of time steps in which the processes represented in the model are expected to equilibrate (or otherwise the equilibrium value may be estimated as for the EECS notion):**TODO** ²³

- **transient:** To obtain a quantity of transient commitment $ccc_{tr} : Val_c$ for a reference state x_{ref} at time t_{ref} that is reached after n_{ref} times steps with respect to a particular time t , which is reached after n_{tr} time steps in the numerical simulation, compute the trajectories

$$x_{s_{tr}} = trajectory(n_{tr}, x_0) \quad \text{and} \quad x_{s_{ref}} = trajectory(n_{ref}, x_0)$$

and then

$$ccc_{tr} = (compare Val_o \circ map(observe \circ aggregateState))(x_{s_{tr}}, x_{s_{ref}}).$$

- **equilibrium:** To obtain a quantity of equilibrium commitment $ccc_{eq} : Val_c$, we need either to choose a number n_{eq} of computation steps that is sufficiently large to let the model reach an equilibrium or a function $estimate_{eq} : List(X) \rightarrow X$ to compute an equilibrium state (as in Section 4). In the first case, the computation does not differ from the transient case. In the second case, one computes an equilibrium notion of commitment by first computing the trajectory

$$x_{s_{ref}} = trajectory(n_{ref}, x_0)$$

and then

$$ccc_{eq} = (compare Val_o \circ map(observe))(estimate_{eq}(xs), aggregateX(x_{s_{ref}})).$$

The commitment experiment suggests to slightly update the comparison experiment as defined in Eq. (29) to allow the two trajectories that are to be compared to have different lengths:

$$\begin{aligned} comparisonExperiment &: (List^2(X) \rightarrow Val_c) \times \mathbb{N}_{<N}^2 \times X^2 \rightarrow Val_c \\ comparisonExperiment(compare, n, n', x, x') & \\ &= (compare \circ map(trajectory))((n, x), (n', x')) \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Then a commitment experiment can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} commitmentExperiment &: \mathbb{N}_{<N}^2 \times X^2 \rightarrow Val_c \\ commitmentExperiment(n, n', x, x') & \\ &= comparisonExperiment(compare Val_o \circ map(observe \circ aggregateX), n, n', x, x') \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

²³Michel: Maybe rearrange a little?

Remarks. As for the CS experiments, we could consider non-deterministic variants and different algorithmic ways of performing measuring, aggregation and comparison operations.

The notion of commitment seeks to quantify how much more climate change is inevitably to be expected at some moment in time – however it crucially depends on the future forcing that is considered. This suggests to consider a notion of multi-scenario commitment in which the considered forcing scenarios represent different policy options, possibly weighted by a judgement about feasibility. With the expected presence of tipping points in the climate system (see Section 6), one might also ask under which forcing scenarios present day or future commitment for some climatic variable entails the crossing of such tipping points. These ideas are explored in TiPES Deliverable 6.3. In [Bot+21] (part of TiPES D6.2), the idea of commitment is used in a stylised way as criterion for partitioning the state space of a dynamical system into desirable and undesirable regions, reminiscent of Heitzig et al.’s topological classification in [Hei+16] and the planetary boundaries/safe operating space concept of [Roc+09].

5.5 Selected references

- Ramanathan [Ram88] is the first to use the term “committed” in the sense of *climate change commitment*.
- Whitherald et al. [WSD01] consider a notion of *warming commitment*.
- Wigley’s paper [Wig05] is the source of the terminology and most of the variants of the *climate change commitment* notion in the IPCC glossary.
- The glossary of the IPCC report Global Warming of 1.5°C[IPC18] includes an entry on *Climate change commitment*, distinguishing between different instances depending on the forcing scenario considered.
- Chapter 12 of IPCC AR5[Kri+13] discusses *climate change commitment*.
- Plattner et al. [Pla+08] use different EMICs to compute the kinds of climate change commitment discussed by the IPCC.
- Lenton et al. [Len+08; Len+19] use the word “committed” in the context of tipping points and tipping elements (cf. Section 6.4) but no explanation is provided to what they explicitly mean by committed.
- Pattyn et al. [Pat+18, Box 2] relate “climate commitment” and tipping points in a study of Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets at 1.5C warming, without further definition of the notion, but likely referring to *sea level rise commitment* in the sense of the IPCC.
- Heitzig [Hei19] uses the notion of *conditional commitment* in the sense of contractual obligations in a game-theoretic setting.
- Feltus and Petit [FP09] propose a *commitment modality* for deontic logic.

6 Abrupt Change, Tipping Point, Tipping Element

This section is concerned with notions related to *abrupt changes* in the Earth system, in particular *tipping point* and *tipping element*.

Definitions. The IPCC glossary entries provide the following definitions (cf. Appendix I.6):

- an *abrupt change* in a system is a change that “takes place substantially faster than the rate of change in the recent history of the affected component of a system”
- if the “abrupt change occurs because the system state actually becomes unstable, such that the subsequent rate of change is independent of the forcing” it is referred to as *tipping point*

- A *tipping point* is “defined as a critical threshold beyond which a system reorganizes, often abruptly and/or irreversibly”
- where a “perturbed state of a dynamical system is defined as *irreversible* on a given timescale, if the recovery from this state due to natural processes takes substantially longer than the timescale of interest” (*emphasis added*)

This description of *abrupt change* corresponds to the definition given in a 2002 *National Research Council (NRC)* report on “abrupt climate change” [BC+02]:

Abrupt climate change

Definition from [BC+02, p.14]:

“Technically, an abrupt climate change occurs when the climate system is forced to cross some *threshold*, triggering a *transition* to a new state at a rate determined by the climate system itself and faster than the cause.” (*emphasis added*)

It should be noted that the usage of “state” in the above descriptions apparently differs from how we have used it in the previous sections. Here “state” rather seems to refer to a *region* of the system’s state space which contains states that are qualitatively distinct from the states in other regions. For a system with state space X in our sense, such a region $R \subset X$ could be described with a predicate $P : X \rightarrow Prop$ such that for all states $x : X$,

$$x \in R \Leftrightarrow P(x).$$

A possible terminology for such qualitatively different regions of the state space could be to consider them as *macro states*, while the individual elements of the state space of a system could be referred to as *micro states*.

Example 6. Alley et al. [All+03] illustrate the idea of abrupt change by the concrete example of flipping a canoe, while introducing the notions of *trigger*, *amplifier*, *globaliser* and *source of persistence* as typical ingredients that bring about such changes after crossing a *threshold*:

“Systems exhibiting *threshold* behavior are familiar. For example, leaning slightly over the side of a canoe will cause only a small tilt, but leaning slightly more may roll you and the craft into the lake. An abrupt change, of a canoe or the climate, requires a *trigger*, such as you leaning out of a canoe; an *amplifier* and *globalizer*, such as the friction between you and the canoe that causes the boat to flip with you; and a *source of persistence*, such as the resistance of the upside-down canoe to being flipped back over.” (*emphasis added*)

Alley et al. also point out that

“Such large and rapid threshold transitions between distinct states are exhibited by many climate models, including simplified models of the oceanic thermohaline circulation [Sto61], atmospheric energy-balance models [Sel69], and atmospheric dynamical models exhibiting spontaneous regime changes [Lor63].” (*citations adapted*)

Kuehn [Kue11] formalises a notion of *critical transition* using the theory of slow-fast dynamical systems. He lists the following attributes of critical transitions (citing [Sch+09]):

- occurrence of an abrupt qualitative change in the system
- the change occurs rapidly relative to the regular system dynamics
- the system crosses a special threshold near a transition
- the new state of the system after the transition is “far away” from its previous state.

Ashwin et al. [Ash+12] point out that the more recently popularised notion of *tipping point* is related to a much older question in climate science:

“The recent interest in tipping points is related to a long-standing question in climate science: to understand whether climate fluctuations and transitions between different ‘states’ are due to external causes (such as variations in the insolation or orbital parameters of the Earth) or to internal mechanisms (such as the oceanic and atmospheric feedbacks acting on different time scales).”

In the following, we will briefly address abrupt changes in paleo data, stability and tipping in climate models and the study of different kinds of tipping behaviour in deterministic and stochastic dynamical systems.

6.1 Abrupt Changes in Time Series

The probably simplest example of a “regime change” is the transition between “warm” and “cold” states of the Earth between *greenhouse periods* (in which no continental glaciers exist) and *glaciations* (ice ages, “Snowball Earth”) with an $\approx 100,000$ yr periodicity documented in proxy records [Sha00]. Very prominently, the notion of *abrupt change* in time series of paleo records is used for events that occurred during glacial or interglacial periods (colder or warmer periods within a glaciation). Alley et al. [All+03] describe such changes as follows:

“For example, global-mean temperature changes of perhaps 5°C to 6°C over ice-age cycles [Bro02] are generally believed to have resulted from small, globally averaged net forcing [All+03, elaboration (5)]. More surprisingly, regional changes over 10 years without major external forcing were in many cases one-third to one-half as large as changes over the 100,000-year ice-age cycles [Bro02; Sto00].” (*citations adapted*)

and

“Regional climate changes of as much as 8° to 16°C [Sto00; Sev+98] occurred repeatedly in as little as a decade or less” (*citations adapted*)

Example 7. *Dansgaard-Oeschger (D-O) events.* The first concrete evidence that the climate system has undergone abrupt changes in the past was found in Greenland ice core records [Dan+82; Dan+84; Oes+84; Dan+93; Ank+93] in the 1980s. Stocker [Sto00] writes:

“The most detailed and continuous information about climate variability comes from the Greenland ice cores (Fig. 4). Hans Oeschger [Oes+84], Willy Dansgaard [Dan+84] and colleagues were the first to recognise the climatic significance of short interstadials (warming events) during the last glacial period; they were numbered consecutively [Dan+93] and later named ‘Dansgaard/Oeschger Events [BD89] (see Fig. 5). All events exhibit a striking similarity in their temporal evolution: cooling extends generally over many centuries to about 3 kyr, while warming is abrupt and occurs within years or decades. This suggests that one common mechanism may be responsible for these climate swings. The recurrence time for the shorter D/O events is of the order of 1000 years.” (*citations adapted, figure references for the original paper*)

Similar recurring oscillations have been found in other records:

- *Heinrich events* are recognised as sequences of iceberg discharges that left [ice rafted?] [debris?] in the North Atlantic [Hei88; Bro+92; Bon+93]/ They are linked to Antarctic Warming Events [WFR09] and thought to be linked to the D-O events
- *Bond events* are climate fluctuations in Holocene records that have a much smaller amplitude than D-O events [Bon+97]

Section 4.1 of [Sto00] provides an overview of “abrupt climate change documented” in paleo records. These proxy records are considered as evidence that there were “repeated, large, abrupt shifts in Northern Hemisphere climate during the last ice age” [All00; Bar+11]. The implications of such abrupt shifts for present day climate change started (at the latest) to be discussed around 2000 with a National Research Council report and several accompanying papers [All00; All+03; BC+02]. There have been diverse efforts to explain the causes of D-O events. The question concerning internal vs external causes as stated in the Ashwin et al. quote in the introduction of this section is mirrored in these efforts. To this day, there is no consensus as to the cause of the D-O events, but it is commonly accepted that they are linked to changes in the location and intensity of water convection in the North Atlantic, with global impacts both on the atmospheric and the oceanic circulation measured, among others, in the isotopic signatures of the south Asian monsoon and Antarctic precipitation.

Methods. Different approaches to paleoclimate modelling in general are described in [Cru12]. A method to explore the possible underlying dynamics of D-O events is described and employed by Lohmann and Ditlevsen [LD19]. Ditlevsen et al. [DAS07] explicitly discuss how DO events and periodicity have been defined in the literature.

6.2 Multi-stability and tipping in conceptual climate models

It was known long before the more recent discussion of *tipping points* that “large and rapid threshold transitions between distinct states are exhibited by many climate models” [All+03].

Early examples of such models include those by Stommel [Sto61]²⁴, Budyko[Bud69], Sellers[Sel69] and Lorenz [Lor63] mentioned in Section 2. These are conceptual models that are studied using dynamical systems and bifurcation theory [Kuz13; Arn+13]. A model is called *multi-stable* if it has more than one stable equilibrium.

Stommel’s model concerns the strength of the thermohaline circulation in the Atlantic and the qualitative distinction between possible equilibria is whether the circulation is “on” or “off”.²⁵

The Budyko and Sellers model are EBMs modelling the Earth’s radiative fluxes at the top of the atmosphere. An early stability study of such a model was conducted by Ghil [Ghi76]. Another simple EBM in which the number of equilibrium states depends on the value of a certain parameter was proposed by Fraedrich[Fra79] and extended to a stochastic model by Sutera[Sut81].

Prototypically, such “large and rapid threshold transitions” can be explained by the presence of *bifurcations* in the model: a bifurcation occurs “when a small smooth change to a parameter (or parameters) of a system causes a sudden qualitative or topological change to its behaviour” [Len13], e.g. the set of equilibrium solutions of the system changes. However, not all forms of *tipping point behaviour* are caused by a bifurcation. Lenton writes [Len13]:

“There are [...] several mathematically distinct potential sources of *tipping point behavior* (where a small change gives rise to a large response in a system).” (*emphasis added*)

and defines tipping point as follows:

Tipping Point

Definition following [Len13]:

A tipping point is a point at which a small perturbation can cause a qualitative change in the future state of a system.

The formulation “the future state” seems [again to refer to a region of the state space](#).

²⁴The variant of this model discussed in Examples 1 and 4 exhibits the same multi-stability.

²⁵According to the appendix of [Mar00], Stommel’s 1961 model “went virtually unnoticed for 25 years” while “in 1982 another box model was independently proposed” (the Rooth model [Roo82]) “that explained how a two-hemispheric THC [...] might become unstable”. Finally, it “was extensively applied to the steady-state pole-to-pole circulation” by Marotzke [MW91; Mar94] and Rahmstorf [Rah96].

Different causes of tipping. In the literature, different kinds of tipping point behaviour are considered which allow to classify critical transitions by their cause. To our knowledge, the following have been discussed:

Classification of Tipping

- *B-tipping*: bifurcation-induced [Ash+12]
- *N-tipping*: noise-induced [Ash+12]
- *R-tipping*: rate-dependent [Ash+12] (e.g. the “compost-bomb instability” [Wie+11])
- *S-tipping*: shock-induced [HF20]
- *P-tipping*: phase-sensitive [ATW21]

B-tipping may occur in a dynamical system m with parameters of type P for which a critical value $p_{\text{cr}} : P$ exists at which the number or stability of equilibrium solutions of the system changes. When the value of this parameter changes due to a forcing $f : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow P$ ²⁶ such that the critical value is crossed, the trajectories of the forced system may pass through states that approach different equilibrium solutions before and after the crossing of the critical value. These different equilibrium solution may in turn correspond to very different observations.

N-tipping may occur in stochastic dynamical systems with multiple equilibrium solutions when noise can cause a trajectory to transition between two states which are attracted by different equilibrium solutions.

R-tipping may occur if such a transition between states leading to different equilibria is triggered when the forcing exceeds a critical rate of change.

S-tipping may occur if such a transition between states leading to different equilibria can be caused by a large perturbation (a shock or extreme event) in the forcing.

Finally, *P-tipping* may occur in cyclic systems in which the possibility of transitioning to a qualitatively different state space region may depend not only on the crossing of a critical parameter value but also on the current phase of the cycle.

Ashwin et al. [Ash+12] show that dynamical systems can exhibit B-, N- and R-tipping behaviour independently or in combination. A simple EBM, the Faedrich-Sutera model [Fra79; Sut81], is shown by Ashwin et al. to exhibit B-, N- and R-tipping.

6.3 Tipping in complex climate models

With the increasing evidence that thresholds for climate tipping points could be crossed as consequence of anthropogenic forcing, concerns have arisen that state of the art climate models may be “too stable”: if they are unable to adequately capture abrupt changes as observed in paleo data, they might not reliably predict abrupt changes in the near future either [Val11]. This concern links to the key question stated in the TiPES proposal for WP2: “Are our models too stable?”.

In a recent review article Brovkin et al. [Bro+21] state that

“For Earth system modellers, the main task is the further improvement of their models and coupled atmosphere-ocean-biosphere-cryosphere processes. Good progress is being made with Earth System Models[Fla11]; they are capable of simulating some abrupt changes, especially in the cryosphere, during the past century and in future projections[Dri+15]. However, they are challenged by attempts to reconstruct abrupt events

²⁶and at each time $t : \mathcal{T}$ the trajectory of the system is thus determined by $m_{f(t)}$

that are well documented from the past, including meltwater pulses due to ice sheet collapses[BHD10], the rapid release of CO₂ during deglaciation[Mar+14] and abrupt climate and vegetation changes in North Africa during the termination of the AHP[Dem+00].”
(citations adapted from the paper)

This provides motivation for the objectives of TiPES WP2: Assess stability for various ESMs and EMICs (see [box on climate models](#)) and facilitate evaluation of model behaviour relative to proxy data prepared by WP1.

► **TiPES**
Links to
Objectives 2.1,
(2.2), 2.3

6.4 Tipping Points and Tipping Elements

While the notion of *tipping point (TP)*²⁷ in the sense of *abrupt change* already appeared earlier, the notion of *tipping element (TE) in the Earth’s climate system* was introduced in Lenton et al.’s paper [Len+08] (following Lenton and Schellnhuber’s commentary [LS07]). Roughly, a tipping element is a subsystem of the Earth system that “may pass” a tipping point. Being a TE is a mathematical property of a dynamical system.

However, Lenton et al. restrict their focus to a class of such subsystems which they judge as *policy-relevant*. Thus, the definition of policy-relevant TEs consists of two parts: one part defining mathematical properties that a TE must possess, and one part with subjective conditions. The latter might be chosen according to what a policy-maker deems relevant and might be seen as value judgements. The authors point out that in previous literature²⁸, “abrupt changes” were described as occurring

“when the climate system is forced to cross some threshold, triggering a transition to a new state at a rate determined by the climate system itself and faster than the cause”

and consider this a case of a bifurcation with an implicit focus on equilibrium properties and implying “some degree of irreversibility”. They intend to give a definition that is broader than the above:

“(i) we wish to include nonclimatic variables; (ii) there may be cases where the transition is slower than the anthropogenic forcing causing it; (iii) there may be no abruptness, but a slight change in control may have a qualitative impact in the future; and (iv) for several important phase changes, state-of-the-art models differ as to whether the transition is reversible or irreversible (in principle).”

The paper then gives a description of when a component of the Earth system is considered a tipping element exhibiting a tipping point. For a “full formal definition”, the authors point to their [supplementary material](#) Appendix 1, “Formal Definition of a Tipping Element and its associated Tipping Point”. We revisit the formal definition below. An informal short definition following the one given in the main paper is:²⁹

Tipping Element

Let Σ be a subsystem of the Earth system associated with a specific region or collection of regions of the globe and at least subcontinental in scale (length scale of order $\approx 1000km$).

Σ is called a *tipping element* if

- the control parameters of the system can be combined into a single control of type P and
- there exists a critical control value $\rho_{cr} : P$

²⁷Lenton et al. do however not cite a scientific paper for this notion but the book by Gladwell [Gla00] that popularised the notion of “tipping point”. Discussions and critical assessments concerning the usage of the “tipping point” notion in climate science can be found in [RN09; Rus11; Rus15; VHS18].

²⁸citing [BC+02] as in the introduction of this section

²⁹The notions “control parameter” and “control value” can simply be understood as “parameter” and “parameter value”. We conjecture that they are used to indicate that the the parameter values in the systems they are interested in are influenced by policy decisions, and thus subject to being controlled.

such that any significant^a deviation of the control value from ρ_{cr} leads to a qualitative change in the value of a crucial system feature after some observation time, measured wrt a reference value of the feature at the critical value.

^awhere a deviation is considered as “significant” if it is large relative to deviations caused by internal variability of the system

Interestingly, the definition does not explicitly use the notion *tipping point*. The informal introduction to the paper states

The tipping point is the corresponding critical point – in forcing and a feature of the system – at which the future state of the system is qualitatively altered.

The supplementary material of [Len+08] states (on p.3, following the formal definition in which the notion *tipping point* does not occur)

[...] our definition of a tipping element and its associated tipping point at the critical value

which seems to indicate that the critical value is considered as the tipping point. This understanding is confirmed in [Len12]:

“In this definition [Len+08]. the critical threshold (ρ_{cr}) is the tipping point, beyond which a qualitative change occurs.”

In Table 1 of [Len+08], the different TEs are classified with respect to properties of the dynamical systems describing them:

Classification of Tipping Elements

A tipping element is classified by the

- feature of interest of the system with direction of change (increase or decrease)
- control parameter(s)
- critical value(s)
- transition timescale
- global mean warming at which the critical value might be reached
- key impacts

In this definition, the first four items are related to the mathematical definition of TEs, while the last two contain additional information that may help to judge the policy relevance of a TE.

Based on their criteria, Lenton et al. identified the following subsystems as instances of their definition of tipping elements in the Earth system [Len+08, Table 1]:³⁰

Policy-relevant potential Tipping Elements: Lenton et al. Examples

- Arctic summer sea ice ♠
- Greenland ice sheet (*GIS*) ♠
- West Antarctic ice sheet (*WAIS*) ♠
- Atlantic thermohaline circulation (*THC*) ♠
- El Niño-Southern Oscillation (*ENSO*)

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Link to Objectives 1.3, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.5

³⁰(♠ marks TEs that are particularly in the focus of TiPES)

- Indian summer monsoon (*ISM*) ♠
- Sahara/Sahel and West African monsoon (*WAM*)
- Amazon rainforest ♠
- Boreal forest

Example 8. [Len+08, Table 1] characterises the THC as tipping element by the following data:

- feature of the system: amplitude of the overturning stream function, decreasing
- control parameter: freshwater input to the North Atlantic
- critical value: +0.1–0.5 Sv
- transition timescale: 100 yr (gradual)
- expected at global mean warming: +3–5 °C
- key impacts: regional cooling, sea level, ITCZ shift³¹

Lenton et al. also analysed some potential tipping elements which however did either not fulfil one of their TE criteria or there was not sufficient data at the time of writing and further research would be required. To our knowledge, the latest update of the assessment at the time of writing is presented in [McK+; Arm+].

6.5 Mathematical definition.

A mathematical definition of the notion *tipping element* is given in the supplementary material of [Len+08]. The formal framework in which the definition is stated is apparently considered as standard and not introduced in detail. The following is how we understand the essence of the definition translated to the notation of the current document:

Being a tipping element is a property of a subsystem Σ of the climate system. The following data is needed to represent Σ :

- a model of Σ with state space X such that forcing is represented by one time-dependent parameter of type $\mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ (thought of as *control path* for the system).³²
- a start time (thought of as “now”) $t_0 : \mathcal{T}$
- an initial state $x_0 : X$
- for each control path $p : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the function $m_p : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow X$ defined by the model (with t_0 and x_0)

Then Σ is a *tipping element* iff there exist

- a system feature of interest given by a function³³

$$F : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

- an “ethical” time span $T_E : \mathcal{T}$ ($T_E > 0$)

³¹The *Intertropical Convergence Zone* is the tropical rain belt where most of the rain on Earth falls [ABS16].

³²The codomain type of the forcing, and similar for the system feature F below, is not explicitly stated by Lenton et al. Since it must be possible to add and subtract values of these types, to take their absolute value and to compare them, we used \mathbb{R} as a reasonable choice. But the original definition might be intended to be more general such that any type with the necessary structure could be used.

³³In [Len+08] this is said to be a projection from high-dimensional state space onto the component of interest. It is similar in spirit the function *observe* we used in the previous sections.

- a “critical” time $t_{\text{cr}} : \mathcal{T}$ $(t_{\text{cr}} < t_0 + T_E)$
- a “critical” control path $p_{\text{cr}} : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$
- an “exceedance time” $T_R : \mathcal{T}$ $(T_R < t_0 + T_E - t_{\text{cr}})$
- a value $\delta : \mathbb{R}$ describing a small variation of the control value $(\delta > 0)$
- a reference control path $p_{\text{ref}} : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$
such that $\forall t \in [t_0, t_0 + T_E], p_{\text{ref}}(t) < p_{\text{cr}}(t_{\text{cr}})$
and $\forall t \in [t_{\text{cr}}, t_{\text{cr}} + T_R], |p_{\text{ref}}(t) - p_{\text{cr}}(t_{\text{cr}})| < \delta/2$
- a time scale T_v to filter variability $(T_v \ll T_E)$
- a value $\hat{F} : \mathbb{R}$ $\hat{F} > 0$
that expresses a qualitative change in the value of the feature F

such that

- I. Every control path which over the ethical horizon $[t_0, t_0 + T_E]$ is in the $\delta/2$ neighbourhood of p_{ref} and does not exceed $p_{\text{cr}}(t_{\text{cr}})$, compared to the reference path only leads to small changes (relative to \hat{F}) of the value of the feature F averaged over T_v -windows in the interval $[t_{\text{cr}}, t_0 + T_E]$:

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\forall t \in [t_0, t_0 + T_E], \quad |p(t) - p_{\text{ref}}(t)| < \delta/2 \quad \wedge \quad p(t) < p_{\text{cr}}(t_{\text{cr}})) \\
& \implies \\
& \forall t \in [t_{\text{cr}}, t_0 + T_E], \quad |\langle F \rangle_t(m_p) - \langle F \rangle_t(m_{p_{\text{ref}}})| \ll \hat{F}
\end{aligned}$$

- II. Any control path $p : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that exceeds the critical value ρ_{cr} by δ at least in the interval $[t_{\text{cr}}, t_{\text{cr}} + T_R]$, leads within $[t_{\text{cr}}, t_0 + T_E]$ to the observation of a qualitative change $\geq \hat{F}$ relative to its development under the reference path p_{ref} :

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\forall t \in [t_{\text{cr}}, t_{\text{cr}} + T_R], \quad p(t) \geq p_{\text{cr}}(t_{\text{cr}}) + \delta) \\
& \implies \\
& \exists T \in [t_{\text{cr}}, t_0 + T_E], \quad \langle F \rangle_T(m_p) - \langle F \rangle_T(m_{p_{\text{ref}}}) \geq \hat{F}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\langle F \rangle_t(x) : \mathbb{R}$ (with $x : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow X$) denotes the T_v -moving average of $F \circ x$ at time $t : \mathcal{T}$.³⁴ Lenton et al. remark that this definition simplifies if T_R and T_E are long enough to let the system reach an equilibrium. They say that the system is now to be assumed as autonomous, which we understand in the sense that now the model is not parameterised by a time-dependent forcing but by a constant control parameter. Denoting the equilibrium value of the system feature F reached by the system with a control parameter $\rho : \mathbb{R}$ by $F_{\text{eq}}(m_{\text{const}(\rho)}) : \mathbb{R}$ ³⁵, they define: Σ is a tipping element if there exists a control parameter with a critical value $\rho_{\text{cr}} : \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$|F_{\text{eq}}(m_{\text{const}(\rho_{\text{cr}} + \delta)}) - F_{\text{eq}}(m_{\text{const}\rho_{\text{cr}}})| \geq \hat{F}.$$

For reference, we also recall the definition given by Lenton et al. to define under which conditions a tipping element is considered as policy-relevant.

A tipping element Σ as defined above is called a *policy-relevant tipping element*, iff the following two conditions are fulfilled:

³⁴The exact definition of $\langle F \rangle$ is not given in the paper, but we would expect

$$\langle F \rangle_t(x) = \frac{\int_{t - \frac{T_v}{2}}^{t + \frac{T_v}{2}} x(t) dt}{T_v}.$$

³⁵where $\text{const}(\rho) : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the constant function that returns ρ for any input

- III. the development of the control path within a political time horizon $T_P \approx 100$ yrs (driven by human interference) determines that a critical state will be reached at some point within T_E . “This may either be the case if the critical state is reached already within the political horizon, or if it would be reached at a later point in time in the absence of policies enacted during the political horizon to prevent the system from reaching its critical state.”
- IV. the qualitative change \hat{F} of the value of the system feature F “could significantly affect human welfare on at least a sub-continental scale, or could compromise the overall mode of operation of the Earth system, or would entail the loss of a unique value of the biosphere”.

Lenton et al. suggest the following concrete values or rules for the choice of T_v, T_E, δ and \hat{F} :

- $T_v \approx 10$ yrs
 (“A reasonable choice for the time scale to filter variability in the system feature F [...] assuming that higher-frequency variations [...] are not relevant for the assessment whether or not a qualitative change \hat{F} has occurred”)
- $\delta \approx 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ “for the particular case of annual global mean temperature”
- $T_E \approx 1000$ yrs “beyond which changes in the Earth system may not matter for current policy considerations”
- “ \hat{F} should be determined by considering associated impacts that fulfil requirement IV” or more general \hat{F} should be “significantly larger than the standard deviation of natural variability” of the feature F on the time scale T_v

Remarks. While T_v, δ, T_E and \hat{F} are existentially quantified in the definition of TE, the latter recommendations concerning the choice of concrete values for these variables suggest to restrict them to fixed values. To our understanding, the definition in this form has the advantage that it first describes the notion of TE in a purely mathematical sense which is applicable to a dynamical system independently of any physical and/or political interpretation. The policy-relevant part of the definition then restricts the class of TEs a posteriori. However, this approach makes the definition also rather difficult to parse. Maybe a simplified version of policy-relevant TE could instead be parameterised by F, T_E and \hat{F} as political parameters and T_v, δ as physical parameters? Then a TE with respect to $(T_E, F, \hat{F}), (T_v, \delta)$ would be witnessed by choices of $t_{cr}, p_{cr}, T_R, p_{ref}$ that fulfil the coherence conditions and conditions I+II.

Another possibility to make the definition of TE more readable might be to introduce predicates like Near, Exceeds, FarAway etc. that describe the properties for control paths and trajectories used in conditions I+II.

6.6 Selected references

- Early multi-stable models: [Sto61], [Sel69], [Lor63], [Bud69]
- Early papers concerning D-O events: [Dan+82; Dan+84; Oes+84; Dan+93; Ank+93]
- Stocker [Sto00] gives an extensive overview of evidence for abrupt climate change in paleo records.
- Early papers addressing abrupt climate change more generally: [All00; All+03; BC+02]
- The original paper introducing the notion of *tipping element* is [Len+08]. A recent “updated assessment” of TEs is [Arm+].
- Different causes for tipping are introduced and studied in [Ash+12], [HF20], [ATW21].
- Kuehn [Kue11; Kue13] formalises the notion of *critical transition* in the framework of fast-slow systems.

- Valdes [Val11] discusses whether state of the art complex climate models are “too stable”.
- The [EU Horizon 2020 project COACCH](#) has studied the potential impacts of climate and socio-economic tipping points for Europe [Gin+18; Trö+17].
- Recent work on “positive” non-climate tipping points: [Len20; Win+20; SL21]
- Russill et al. [RN09; Rus11; Rus15; VHS18] critically assess the usage of “tipping point” as *generating metaphor* in climate change communication.
- Lately there has been much interest in possible *tipping cascades*, e.g. [Krö+20; Loh+21; Klo+21; Bro+21; Wun+21].

7 Early Warning Signal

The observation that the climate system has undergone abrupt transitions in the past does not only trigger the question whether it might do so in the future, potentially as a consequence of human behaviour. It also suggests to ask whether there are ways to predict (and if possible prevent) imminent abrupt changes. The question of predictability has already been raised with the first papers explicitly focusing on abrupt climate change, e.g. in the context of the relation between D-O events and the thermohaline circulation: Marotzke’s paper [Mar00] includes paragraphs “Would we Know Were It Happening Today?” and “A Different Brand of Predictability”, and [Sto00] concludes with the importance of efforts to detect “early signs of sustained thermohaline circulation changes in the near future”. With respect to ecosystems, the question of the predictability of approaching critical transitions has been posed even much earlier: Wissel [Wis84] discusses “a universal law for the characteristic return time near thresholds”:

“(a)[...] we search for a general property of ecosystems which is specific for the neighbourhood of thresholds; (b) [...] we ask if it is theoretically possible to use this property for the prediction of the position of a threshold”

In climate science, Tziperman [Tzi00] and Knutti/Stocker [KS02] describe the behaviour of the thermohaline circulation close to an instability threshold (the former based on simulations with a comprehensive climate model, the latter with a model of intermediate complexity). Consecutively, a variety of methods is proposed for the detection of approaching critical transitions. An overview of the proposed methods (illustrated by an application to simulated ecological data) is given in [Dak+12] (see also below). A more recent discussion on methods can be found in the introduction of [BBA20].

The notion *Early Warning Signal* seems to have been introduced by Dakos et al. in [Dak+08]:

“our way to detect slowing down might be used as a universal early warning signal for upcoming catastrophic change”

and more prominently in Scheffer et al.’s “Early-warning signals for critical transitions” [Sch+09], in which the authors write

“work in different scientific fields is now suggesting the existence of generic early-warning signals that may indicate for a wide class of systems if a critical threshold is approaching”

Surprisingly, the notion of *Early Warning Signal (EWS)* or *Early Warning Sign* does not seem to appear in the IPCC glossary as of yet. Recently, Brovkin et al. [Bro+21, Box 1] write about EWS in their terminology introduction:

Early Warning Signals (EWS)

“[...] are quantitative indicators of the proximity of a system to a tipping point[Dak+08]. EWS apply mathematical principles of dynamical systems to Earth system components. EWS could be measured in one-dimensional space (such as time series of dust deposition in a marine core) using uni-variate precursors (for example, increasing temporal autocorrelation) or in multi-dimensional space (such as spatial patterns of vegetation cover) applying spatially explicit precursors” (*citation adapted*)

A lot of information on EWS is provided by [Dak+12]) on the [EWS Tool Box Website](#) [Dak+]. Dakos et al.[Dak+12] distinguish between *metric-based* and *model-based* methods for detecting EWS. Both kinds “reflect changes in the properties of the observed time-series” considered as generated by a stochastic dynamical system

“*Metric-based* indicators quantify changes in the statistical properties of the time series [...] without attempting to fit the data with a specific model structure. *Model-based* methods quantify changes in the time series by attempting to fit the data to a model that is based on the general structure of” [*the generating model*]. “The ultimate goal of both types of indicators is to capture changes in the ‘memory’ (i.e. correlation structure) and variability of a time series and to determine if they follow patterns as predicted by models of critical transitions, while the system is approaching a transition into an alternative dynamic regime”

Caveats. Based on the example of the [D-O events](#), Ditlevsen et al.[DJ10] point out two important provisos concerning the hope for detecting approaching abrupt changes by EWS. The first proviso concerns increased variance and increased autocorrelation as two generic characteristics indicating the approach of a bifurcation point:

“These two signals are connected, and the detection of only one and not the other cannot be taken as a sign of an approaching tipping point. This is contrary to what was recently claimed [Dak+08; Sch+09].” (*citations adapted*)

The second proviso concerns the [D-O events](#) as “most clearly observed transition [...] besides the glacial-interglacial transitions themselves”. Ditlevsen et al. investigate whether increased variance and increased autocorrelation can be detected in the NGRIP records [Mem04], arriving at the conclusion that D-O events are “most probably not generated by bifurcations: They are noise-induced transitions without early warning signals.”

Subsequent research by Rypdal [Ryp16] and Boers [Boe18] however reports the presence of statistical EWS for D-O events. Yet it is important to note that not all abrupt changes – e.g. because they are noise- instead of bifurcation-induced – may be preceded by EWS. And also the possibility of false positives has to be taken into consideration. As Boers writes [Boe18]:

“The fact that a forthcoming bifurcation implies the presence of EWS does, however, not exclude the possibility that statistical fluctuations indistinguishable from EWS arise either by chance or by other mechanisms unrelated to a bifurcation or abrupt transition.”

And the authors of [Kéf+13] point out concerning EWS based on “critical slowing down”:

“slowing down generally happens in situations where a system is becoming increasingly sensitive to external perturbations, independent of whether the impeding change is catastrophic or not. These results highlight that indicators specific to catastrophic shifts are still lacking.”

Livina, Ditlevsen and Lenton also address the criticism of [DJ10] by “blind testing” methods of detecting multiple system states and bifurcations in time series data [LDL12]: Time series data was

provided by one author who knew the underlying model from which the data was generated, while the other two authors used different methods to analyse the data, “described the expected properties and behaviour of the underlying systems and attempted to model the corresponding data”. They conclude:

“In most cases, the methods successfully detected the number of states in a system, and the occurrence of transitions between states. The derived models were able to reproduce the test data accurately. However, noise-induced abrupt transitions between existing states cannot be forecast due to the lack of any change in the underlying potential.”

Methods. We have seen that the notion *Early Warning Signal* refers to various statistical indicators for the approach of abrupt transitions in time series (often thought of as induced by bifurcations). A concrete step-by-step illustration of analysing time series data to detect approaching transitions is given in [Dak+12]. The data may come from proxy data or observations, or may have been generated by model simulation. Given a time-series as input, the procedure very roughly consists of

- pre-processing the data to obtain a *regular* time series, (i.e. there are no missing values and the data is equally spaced in time) without distorting its statistical properties
- filtering to eliminate non-stationarities in the mean of the time series (as they “can cause spurious indications of impending transitions”) and detrending to remove e.g. seasonal trends (since they would “impose a strong correlation structure on the time series”)
- apply one or (better) multiple methods to test the data for the presence of EWS.
 - metric-based: compute how certain statistical metrics for the time series, e.g. *variance*, *autocorrelation*, *skewness*³⁶ change along the time series;
 - model-based: fit the data to a specific kind of model, e.g. a *drift-diffusion-jump*, a *time-varying AR(p)* or a *threshold AR(p)* model. Properties of the fitted models then can be used as indicators.
- perform a sensitivity analysis by varying underlying choices of parameters in the previous steps, e.g. when using a *rolling window* method by altering the window size or the degree of smoothing for used in filtering.
- perform a significance test for the obtained results (whether EWS are considered to occur in the time series or not), especially to avoid false positives (type I errors); how this can be done depends on which method has been employed to test for EWS.

7.1 Selected references

- Wissel [Wis84] already studied indicators for approaching thresholds for ecosystems.
- Marotzke addresses the question predictability for a possible collapse of the THC [Mar00].
- Early papers suggesting data analysis methods to detect approaching thresholds: [KHP03; HK04; LL07]
- First papers explicitly using the term “EWS”: [Dak+08; Sch+09]
- Noise-induced abrupt transitions might not be preceded by EWS: [DJ10]; blind testing detection methods: [LDL12]
- There might also be false positives: EWS before “non-catastrophic” transitions [Kéf+13].

³⁶i.e. how asymmetric the distribution of values of the time series is

- Kuehn suggests the mathematical theory of deterministic and stochastic *slow-fast* systems as providing a natural framework for studying critical transitions and EWS [Kue11; Kue13; Kue15]
- Comparison and robustness testing of methods: [Len+12]
- Recent paper on using spectral analysis to detect more specific EWS that contain more information about the type of underlying bifurcation: [BBA20]
- EWS in paleo data: [LKL10; Ryp16; Boe18]

► **TiPES**
Line of work
leading to
Objective 5.3

► **TiPES**
Line of work
leading to
Objectives
1.1,1.2 and 1.4

8 Toward an ontology

Recapitulating the different objects, notions and computational patterns we have encountered in this report, we might consider a number of abstract concepts to organise them in the style of an ontology. In the following we sketch some ideas without being conclusive.

Consider the following two basic classes of objects (parameterised over types $\mathcal{I}, \mathcal{I}_1, \mathcal{I}_2, D, I, Val$):

- Sequential data that might be thought of as temporally ordered but potentially distributed in space (like *observation data, proxy records, trajectories of dynamical systems*)

$$SeqData_{\mathcal{I},D} = \mathcal{I} \rightarrow D$$

for a strictly ordered index type \mathcal{I} and type of data D . An example of this could be a regular time series $\mathcal{T} \rightarrow X$ or the result of a numerical simulation $[x_0, \dots, x_n]$ represented as function $\mathbb{N}_{<n} \rightarrow X$.

- Producers of sequential data (like *physical measurements or models of the climate system*) represented as functions that given some input I return a sequence of data:

$$SeqDataProducer_{I,\mathcal{I},D} = I \rightarrow SeqData_{\mathcal{I},D}.$$

In the case of measurements the “input” could be collected by sensors and associated to a time-stamp to produce sequential data for further usage; for a dynamical system, the input could be an initial time and state, used to produce a trajectory as output.

Note that each *SeqData* object can be considered as a constant *SeqDataProducer*.

Given these two base classes of objects, we might consider the following classes of operations:

- Transformations of sequential data

$$SeqDataTr_{\mathcal{I}_1,\mathcal{I}_2,D,\mathcal{T}} = List(SeqData_{\mathcal{I}_1,D}) \rightarrow SeqData_{\mathcal{I}_2,D}$$

e.g. various operations on time series like *dating, removing biases or stacking*.

- Statistical analysis of sequential data

$$SeqDataStatAnalysis_{\mathcal{I},D} = SeqData_{\mathcal{I},D} \rightarrow Val$$

e.g. computing measures like variance, auto-correlation or simply the expected value.

- Comparison experiments in which, given one or more *SeqDataProducer* m_i and a list of inputs, the output produced by the m_i when applied to the different inputs is compared

$$ComparisonExperiment_{I,\mathcal{I},D,Val} = List(SeqDataProducer_{I,\mathcal{I},D}) \times List(I) \rightarrow Val$$

as e.g. seen in the computations of CS and commitment based on *comparisonExperiment* (Eq. (32)) for the special case in which there is only one *SeqDataProducer*, namely the climate model.

Other, more specific classes of experiments may be based on comparison experiments:

- Calibration experiments

$$\begin{aligned} \text{CalibrationExperiment}_{I,\mathcal{I},D,Val} = \\ (P \rightarrow \text{SeqDataProducer}_{I,\mathcal{I},D}) \times \text{List}(P) \times I \times \text{List}(D) \rightarrow Val \end{aligned}$$

in which, given a family of sequential data producers $\{m_p\}_{p:P}$, a list of possible parameter values $ps : \text{List}(P)$, an input and $\text{SeqData } d : D$ for validation, for example a ranking of the parameter values³⁷ is computed by performing comparison experiments between each instance of m_p (with p from ps) and d (considering d as constant SeqDataProducer). The CS-parameter experiment described in Section 4.1 is an example.

- Perturbation experiments

$$\text{PerturbationExperiment}_{I,\mathcal{I},D,Val} = \text{SeqDataProducer}_{I,\mathcal{I},D} \times I \times (I \rightarrow I) \rightarrow Val$$

in which, given a $\text{SeqDataProducer}_{I,\mathcal{I},D}$ m , an input $i : I$ and a function $\text{perturb} : I \rightarrow I$, a comparison experiment is performed with $[m, m]$ and $[i, \text{perturb}(i)]$ as inputs. The ECS experiment as instance of perturbExperiment in Section 4.1 is an example.

We have classes of properties

- for sequential data

$$\text{SeqDataProp}_{\mathcal{I},D} = \text{SeqData}_{\mathcal{I},D} \rightarrow Val$$

- for sequential data producers

$$\text{SeqDataProducerProp}_{I,\mathcal{I},D} = \text{SeqDataProducer}_{I,\mathcal{I},D} \rightarrow Val$$

where for logical properties $Val = \text{Prop}$ or $Val = \mathbb{B}$; for quantitative properties Val is a numerical type like \mathbb{R} , on which standard arithmetic operations are defined and which carries additional structure like an order $\sqsubseteq : Val \times Val \rightarrow \text{Prop}$ and a metric $\text{compare} : Val \times Val \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

To represent different kinds of uncertainties, we may consider monadic generalisations of the above, for example

$$\text{MSeqData}_{\mathcal{I},D,M} = \mathcal{I} \rightarrow M(D)$$

represented as functions that given some input I return a monadic value of data (e.g. a probability distribution). A generalised form of data producer could in turn produce monadic values of monadic sequential data:

$$\text{MSeqDataProducer}_{I,\mathcal{I},D,M} = I \rightarrow M(\text{MSeqData}_{\mathcal{I},D,M}).$$

where M is the functor of a monad.

In the examples mentioned above, we have already seen how the climate sensitivity and commitment experiments fit in this abstract framework. What about the other notions we have discussed?

We suggest that

- the different variants of climate sensitivity and climate change commitment discussed in this report are quantitative properties of sequential data producers;
- *having abrupt changes* or *having EWS* are logical properties of sequential data;
- *being a tipping element* and *having a tipping point* are logical properties of sequential data producers (which overlap in the Lenton et al. definition);
- *a tipping element* is a sequential data producer that has the above two properties and which moreover can produce data *having abrupt changes*. It is not necessary that it can produce sequential data *having EWS*.

³⁷There are many options what exactly to compute as output: One may just compute one “best” parameter configuration according to some metric, or the best within configurations within a certain range etc.

9 Conclusion

Having reviewed a number of notions relevant for tipping point research, what have we learned? The object that one is ultimately interested in studying is the “real” climate system. As we have seen, climate sensitivity, climate change commitment and abrupt changes concern in a broad sense the response of the climate system or its subsystems to interventions:

- climate sensitivity is an idealised metric for the temperature increase resulting from a doubling of the CO₂ concentration of the atmosphere in an equilibrium state
- climate change commitment is a metric for delayed responses like temperature increase or sea level rise after forcing is stopped or at least not increased anymore in a non-equilibrium state
- abrupt change refers to a qualitative change of the system’s behaviour in response to comparatively small changes in forcing.

Since the climate system is not amenable to systematic and repeatable empirical experiments, these properties can only be studied by analysing observations and studying representations of the system or its subsystems. For this, time series and dynamical systems play a crucial role, and there are generic techniques that are used to study their properties. What we called *comparison experiment* in Sections 4 and 5 is such a generic technique, and similarly the fitting of parameterised models to time series of observations. The methods that are used to study the notions we discussed in this report arise as instances of such generic techniques, and the notions might be studied in more than one way, as we have e.g. seen for climate sensitivity. In the preparation of this report and from discussions in the context of the TiPES project, our impression was that it is difficult to attach unambiguous “meanings” to these notions. This has been noted before. Russill [Rus15] reviews origins, precursors, and debates around the usage of the “tipping point” in the discourse about climate change. He points out that besides the framework of dynamical systems theory, the usage of tipping point in the climate literature is also related to the scientific community inspired by the Gaia theory [Lov72]. Still following [Rus15], the tipping point is a metaphor that has the property of being “generative”: its cultural resonance is intended to “shift popular heuristics for environmental change”. However, the multiple usages of the “tipping point”, stemming from different communities, come at the cost of semantic confusion (see below).

For the notions of abrupt change, TP and EWS, in particular, the usages seem to be evolving. In reviewing the literature, our impression was that descriptions in the first papers on abrupt climate change, tipping and EWS seem inspired by bifurcations in dynamical systems without necessarily saying this explicitly [RN09]. In the line of work by Lenton et al. based on [Len+08], TPs are however understood in a more liberal way, as seen in Section 6.4. This is e.g. discussed in [Len12, pp.11-12] and, again, disagreements arising from different perceptions of what is meant by TP are called *semantic confusion* in [Dua+12]. Similarly, following [Dak+08], the term EWS sometimes seemed to be used as a synonym for *critical slowing down* exhibited by dynamical systems when approaching a bifurcation [DJ10]. But other indicators, also for different kinds of tipping, have been proposed and also called EWS [Dak+12; RS16; Ma+22].

For this report, we have collected informal definitions and classification information that might be used as semantic annotation for different instances of climate sensitivity and commitment experiments, tipping elements and early warning signs. We have furthermore suggested generic schemes of which CS and commitment experiments are instances and discussed Lenton et al.’s formal definition of TEs. Finally, we have suggested an abstract perspective that may help to organise tipping notions in the style of an ontology.

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Conflicts of Interest

None.

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I IPCC Glossary entries

(The AR6 WGI glossary is not yet officially approved, but we use it here to make sure to include the most up-to-date information.)

I.1 Concerning climate models

What the IPCC AR6 WGI Glossary tells us about climate models:

IPCC Glossary: Climate model

A qualitative or quantitative representation of the climate system based on the physical, chemical and biological properties of its components, their interactions and feedback processes and accounting for some of its known properties. The climate system can be represented by models of varying complexity; that is, for any one component or combination of components a spectrum or hierarchy of models can be identified, differing in such aspects as the number of spatial dimensions, the extent to which physical, chemical or biological processes are explicitly represented, or the level at which empirical parametrisations are involved. There is an evolution towards more complex models with interactive chemistry and biology. Climate models are applied as a research tool to study and simulate the climate and for operational purposes, including monthly, seasonal and interannual climate predictions. See also Chemistry-climate model, Earth system model (ESM), Earth system model of intermediate complexity (EMIC), Energy balance model (EBM), Simple climate model (SCM), Regional climate model (RCM), Dynamic global vegetation model (DGVM), General circulation model (GCM) and Emulators.

IPCC Glossary: Process-based model

Theoretical concepts and computational methods that represent and simulate the behaviour of real-world systems derived from a set of functional components and their interactions with each other and the system environment, through physical and mechanistic processes occurring over time.

IPCC Glossary: Integrated assessment model (IAM)

Models that integrate knowledge from two or more domains into a single framework. They are one of the main tools for undertaking integrated assessments. One class of IAM used in respect of climate change mitigation may include representations of: multiple sectors of the economy, such as energy, land use and land use change; interactions between sectors; the economy as a whole; associated greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and sinks; and reduced representations of the climate system. This class of model is used to assess linkages between economic, social and technological development and the evolution of the climate system. Another class of IAM additionally includes representations of the costs associated with climate change impacts, but includes less detailed representations of economic systems. These can be used to assess impacts and mitigation in a cost-benefit framework and have been used to estimate the social cost of carbon.

IPCC Glossary: Simple climate model (SCM)

A broad class of lower-dimensional models of the energy balance, radiative transfer, carbon cycle, or a combination of such physical components. SCMs are also suitable for performing emulations of climate-mean variables of Earth system models (ESMs), given that their structural flexibility can capture both the parametric and structural uncertainties across process-oriented ESM responses. They can also be used to test consistency across multiple lines of evidence with regard to climate sensitivity ranges, transient climate responses (TCRs), transient climate response to cumulative emissions (TCREs) and carbon cycle feedbacks. See also Emulators and Earth system model of intermediate complexity (EMIC).

IPCC Glossary: Earth System Model (ESM)

A coupled atmosphere–ocean general circulation model (AOGCM) in which a representation of the carbon cycle is included, allowing for interactive calculation of atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) or compatible emissions. Additional components (e.g., atmospheric chemistry, ice sheets, dynamic vegetation, nitrogen cycle, but also urban or crop models) may be included. See also Earth system model of intermediate complexity (EMIC).

IPCC Glossary: Earth system Model of Intermediate Complexity (EMIC)

Earth system models of intermediate complexity (EMIC) represent climate processes at a lower resolution or in a simpler, more idealised fashion than an Earth system model (ESM).

IPCC Glossary: Energy balance model (EBM)

An energy balance model is a simplified model that analyses the energy budget of the Earth to compute changes in the climate. In its simplest form, there is no explicit spatial dimension and the model then provides an estimate of the changes in globally averaged temperature computed from the changes in radiation. This zero-dimensional energy balance model can be extended to a one-dimensional or two-dimensional model if changes to the energy budget with respect to latitude, or both latitude and longitude, are explicitly considered.

IPCC Glossary: General circulation model (GCM)

A numerical representation of the atmosphere–ocean–sea ice system based on the physical, chemical and biological properties of its components, their interactions and feedback processes. General circulation models are used for weather forecasts, seasonal to decadal prediction, and climate projections. They are the basis of the more complex Earth system models (ESMs). See also Climate model.

IPCC Glossary: Regional climate model (RCM)

A climate model at higher resolution over a limited area. Such models are used in downscaling global climate results over specific regional domains.

IPCC Glossary: Dynamic global vegetation model (DGVM)

A model that simulates vegetation development and dynamics through space and time, as driven by climate and other environmental changes.

IPCC Glossary: Emulation

Reproducing the behaviour of complex, process-based models (namely, Earth System Models, ESMs) via simpler approaches, using either emulators or simple climate models (SCMs). The computational efficiency of emulating approaches opens new analytical possibilities given that ESMs take a lot of computational resources for each simulation. See also Emulators and Simple climate model (SCM).

IPCC Glossary: Emulators

A broad class of heavily parametrized models ('one-or-few-line climate models'), statistical methods like neural networks, genetic algorithms or other artificial intelligence approaches, designed to reproduce the responses of more complex, process-based Earth System Models (ESMs). The main application of emulators is to extrapolate insights from ESMs and observational constraints to a larger set of emission scenarios. See also Emulation and Simple climate model (SCM).

I.2 Concerning model experiments

IPCC Glossary: Equilibrium and transient climate experiment

An equilibrium climate experiment is a climate model experiment in which the model is allowed to fully adjust to a change in radiative forcing. Such experiments provide information on the difference between the initial and final states of the model, but not on the time-dependent response. If the forcing is allowed to evolve gradually according to a prescribed emission scenario, the time-dependent response of a climate model may be analysed. Such an experiment is called a transient climate experiment. See also *Climate projection*. (AR5, WGI)

IPCC Glossary: Model initialization

A climate prediction typically proceeds by integrating a climate model forward in time from an initial state that is intended to reflect the actual state of the climate system. Available observations of the climate system are 'assimilated' into the model. Initialization is a complex process that is limited by available observations, observational errors and, depending on the procedure used, may be affected by uncertainty in the history of climate forcing. The initial conditions will contain errors that grow as the forecast progresses, thereby limiting the time for which the forecast will be useful.

IPCC Glossary: Parameterisation

In climate models, this term refers to the technique of representing processes that cannot be explicitly resolved at the spatial or temporal resolution of the model (sub-grid scale processes) by relationships between model-resolved larger-scale variables and the area- or time-averaged effect of such subgrid scale processes.

I.3 Concerning model simulations/scenarios/pathways

IPCC Glossary: Pathways

The temporal evolution of natural and/or human systems towards a future state. Pathway concepts range from sets of quantitative and qualitative scenarios or narratives of potential futures to solution-oriented decision-making processes to achieve desirable societal goals. Pathway approaches typically focus on biophysical, techno-economic, and/or socio-behavioural trajectories and involve various dynamics, goals, and actors across different scales. See also Scenario storyline (under Storyline), Mitigation scenario (under Scenario), Baseline scenario (under Scenario) and Stabilisation (of GHG or CO₂-equivalent concentration).

1.5°C pathway A pathway of emissions of greenhouse gases and other climate forcers that provides an approximately one-in-two to two-in-three chance, given current knowledge of the climate response, of global warming either remaining below 1.5°C or returning to 1.5°C by around 2100 following an overshoot.

Representative concentration pathways (RCPs) Scenarios that include time series of emissions and concentrations of the full suite of greenhouse gases (GHGs) and aerosols and chemically active gases, as well as land use/land cover (Moss et al., 2010). The word representative signifies that each RCP provides only one of many possible scenarios that would lead to the specific radiative forcing characteristics. The term pathway emphasises that not only the long-term concentration levels are of interest, but also the trajectory taken over time to reach that outcome (Moss et al., 2010).

RCPs usually refer to the portion of the concentration pathway extending up to 2100, for which Integrated assessment models produced corresponding emission scenarios. Extended concentration pathways describe extensions of the RCPs from 2100 to 2300 that were calculated using simple rules generated by stakeholder consultations, and do not represent fully consistent scenarios. Four RCPs produced from Integrated assessment models were selected from the published literature and are used in the Fifth IPCC Assessment and also used in this Assessment for comparison, spanning the range from approximately below 2°C warming to high (> 4°C) warming best-estimates by the end of the 21st century: RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP6.0 and RCP8.5.

- *RCP2.6*: One pathway where radiative forcing peaks at approximately 3W m^{-2} and then declines to be limited at 2.6W m^{-2} in 2100 (the corresponding Extended Concentration Pathway, or ECP, has constant emissions after 2100).
- *RCP4.5* and *RCP6.0*: Two intermediate stabilisation pathways in which radiative forcing is limited at approximately 4.5W m^{-2} and 6.0W m^{-2} in 2100 (the corresponding ECPs have constant concentrations after 2150).
- *RCP8.5*: One high pathway which leads to $> 8.5\text{W m}^{-2}$ in 2100 (the corresponding ECP has constant emissions after 2100 until 2150 and constant concentrations after 2250).

See also Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) and Shared socio-economic pathways (SSPs) (under Pathways).

Shared socio-economic pathways (SSPs) Shared socio-economic pathways (SSPs) have been developed to complement the Representative concentration pathways (RCPs). By design, the RCP emission and concentration pathways were stripped of their association with a certain socio-economic development. Different levels of emissions and climate change along the dimension of the RCPs can hence be explored against the backdrop of different socio-economic development pathways (SSPs) on the other dimension in a matrix. This integrative SSP-RCP framework is now widely used in the climate impact and policy analysis literature, where climate projections obtained under the RCP scenarios are analysed against the backdrop of various SSPs. As several emission updates were due, a new set of emission scenarios was developed in conjunction with the SSPs. Hence, the abbreviation SSP is now used for two things: On the one hand SSP1, SSP2, ..., SSP5 is used to denote the five socio-economic scenario families. On the other hand, the abbreviations SSP1-1.9, SSP1-2.6, ..., SSP5-8.5 are used to denote the newly developed emission scenarios that are the result of an SSP implementation within an integrated assessment model. Those SSP scenarios are bare of climate policy assumption, but in combination with so-called shared policy assumptions (SPAs), various approximate radiative forcing levels of 1.9, 2.6, ..., or 8.5W m^{-2} are reached by the end of the century, respectively.

IPCC Glossary: Projection

A potential future evolution of a quantity or set of quantities, often computed with the aid of a model. Unlike predictions, projections are conditional on assumptions concerning, for example, future socio-economic and technological developments that may or may not be realised. See also Climate projection, Pathways and Scenario.

IPCC Glossary: Scenario

A plausible description of how the future may develop based on a coherent and internally consistent set of assumptions about key driving forces (e.g., rate of technological change (TC), prices) and relationships. Note that scenarios are neither predictions nor forecasts, but are used to provide a view of the implications of developments and actions. See also Climate scenario and Regional climate scenario.

Baseline scenario See Reference Scenario See Reference scenario (under Scenario).

Concentrations scenario A plausible representation of the future development of atmospheric concentrations of substances that are radiatively active (e.g., greenhouse gases (GHGs), aerosols, tropospheric ozone), plus human-induced land cover changes that can be radiatively active via albedo changes, and often used as input to a climate model to compute climate projections.

Emissions scenario A plausible representation of the future development of emissions of substances that are radiatively active (e.g., greenhouse gases (GHGs) or aerosols), plus human-induced land cover changes that can be radiatively active via albedo changes, based on a coherent and internally consistent set of assumptions about driving forces (such as demographic and socio-economic development, technological change, energy and land use) and their key relationships. Concentration scenarios, derived from emission scenarios, are often used as input to a climate model to compute climate projections. See also Representative concentration pathways (RCPs) (under Pathways) and Shared socio-economic pathways (SSPs) (under Pathways).

Mitigation scenario A plausible description of the future that describes how the (studied) system responds to the implementation of mitigation policies and measures. See also Pathways, Socio-economic scenario (under Scenario) and Stabilisation (of GHG or CO₂-equivalent concentration).

Reference scenario Scenario used as starting or reference point for a comparison between two or more scenarios.

Note 1: In many types of climate change research, reference scenarios reflect specific assumptions about patterns of socio-economic development and may represent futures that assume no climate policies or specified climate policies, for example those in place or planned at the time a study is carried out. Reference scenarios may also represent futures with limited or no climate impacts or adaptation, to serve as a point of comparison for futures with impacts and adaptation. These are also referred to as baseline scenarios in the literature.

Note 2: Reference scenarios can also be climate policy or impact scenarios, which in that case are taken as a point of comparison to explore the implications of other features, e.g., of delay, technological options, policy design and strategy or to explore the effects of additional impacts and adaptation beyond those represented in the reference scenario.

Note 3: The term business as usual scenario has been used to describe a scenario that assumes no additional policies beyond those currently in place and that patterns of socio-economic development are consistent with recent trends. The term is now used less frequently than in the past.

Note 4: In climate change attribution or impact attribution research reference scenarios may refer to counterfactual historical scenarios assuming no anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions (climate change attribution) or no climate change (impact attribution).

Socio-economic scenario A scenario that describes a plausible future in terms of population, gross domestic product (GDP), and other socio-economic factors relevant to understanding the implications of climate change. See also Baseline scenario (under Scenario), Mitigation scenario (under Scenario) and Pathways.

IPCC Glossary: Regional climate scenario

A narrative used to describe how the future might unfold for a region (IPCC-TGICA, 2007). These are often used to guide impact understanding and adaptation efforts. They can include quantitative information based on scaled historical data or derived from GCM-based internally consistent future climates.

See also Climate scenario.

IPCC Glossary: Storyline

A way of making sense of a situation or a series of events through the construction of a set of explanatory elements. Usually it is built on logical or causal reasoning. In climate research, the term storyline is used both in connection to scenarios as related to a future trajectory of the climate and human systems or to a weather or climate event. In this context, storylines can be used to describe plural, conditional possible futures or explanations of a current situation, in contrast to single, definitive futures or explanations.

Physical climate storyline A self-consistent and plausible unfolding of a physical trajectory of the climate system, or a weather or climate event, on timescales from hours to multiple decades (Shepherd et al., 2018). Through this, storylines explore, illustrate and communicate uncertainties in the climate system response to forcing and in internal variability.

Scenario storyline A narrative description of a scenario (or family of scenarios), highlighting the main scenario characteristics, relationships between key driving forces and the dynamics of their evolution.

I.4 Concerning climate sensitivity

IPCC Glossary: Climate metrics

Measures of aspects of the overall climate system response to radiative forcing, such as equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS), transient climate response (TCR), transient climate response to cumulative CO₂ emissions (TCRE) and the airborne fraction of anthropogenic carbon dioxide. See also Greenhouse gas emission metric, Climate indicator and Key climate indicators (under Climate indicator).

IPCC Glossary: Climate sensitivity

The change in the surface temperature in response to a change in the atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration or other radiative forcing. See also Climate feedback parameter.

IPCC Glossary: Earth system sensitivity

The equilibrium surface temperature response of the coupled atmosphere-ocean- cryosphere-vegetation-carbon cycle system to a doubling of the atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration is referred to as Earth System sensitivity. Because it allows ice sheets to adjust to the external perturbation, it may differ substantially from the equilibrium climate sensitivity derived from coupled atmosphere-ocean models.

IPCC Glossary: Equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS)

The equilibrium (steady state) change in the surface temperature following a doubling of the atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration from pre-industrial conditions.

Closely related:

IPCC Glossary: Climate feedback parameter

A way to quantify the radiative response of the climate system to a global surface temperature change induced by a radiative forcing. It is quantified as the change in net energy flux at the top of atmosphere for a given change in annual global surface temperature. It has units of $\text{W m}^{-2} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$.

I.5 Concerning climate commitment

IPCC Glossary: Climate change commitment

Climate change commitment is defined as the unavoidable future climate change resulting from inertia in the geophysical and socio-economic systems. Different types of climate change commitment are discussed in the literature (see subterms). Climate change commitment is usually quantified in terms of the further change in temperature, but it includes other future changes, for example in the hydrological cycle, in extreme weather events, in extreme climate events, and in sea level.

Constant composition commitment The constant composition commitment is the remaining climate change that would result if atmospheric composition, and hence radiative forcing, were held fixed at a given value. It results from the thermal inertia of the ocean and slow processes in the cryosphere and land surface.

Constant emissions commitment The constant emissions commitment is the committed climate change that would result from keeping anthropogenic emissions constant.

Zero emissions commitment The zero emissions commitment is an estimate of the subsequent global warming that would result after anthropogenic emissions are set to zero. It is determined by both inertia in physical climate system components (ocean, cryosphere, land surface) and carbon cycle inertia. In its widest sense it refers to emissions of each climate forcer including greenhouse gases, aerosols and their precursors. The climate response to this can be complex due to the different timescale of response of each climate forcer. A specific sub-category of zero emissions commitment is the Zero CO₂ Emissions Commitment which refers to the climate system response to CO₂ emissions after setting these to net zero. The CO₂-only definition is of specific use in estimating remaining carbon budgets.

I.6 Concerning abrupt climate change

IPCC Glossary: Abrupt change

A change in the system that is substantially faster than the typical rate of the changes in its history.

IPCC Glossary: Abrupt climate change

A large-scale abrupt change in the climate system that takes place over a few decades or less, persists (or is anticipated to persist) for at least a few decades and causes substantial impacts in human and/or natural systems.

IPCC Glossary: Tipping element

A component of the Earth System that is susceptible to a tipping point.

IPCC Glossary: Tipping point

A critical threshold beyond which a system reorganizes, often abruptly and/or irreversibly.

IPCC Glossary: Irreversibility

A perturbed state of a dynamical system is defined as irreversible on a given timescale, if the recovery from this state due to natural processes takes substantially longer than the timescale of interest.

II TiPES work package objectives

In this appendix we list the objectives of WP1–5 for reference.

WP1: Observation-based analysis of tipping elements

1. To provide the empirical basis to study **abrupt climatic transitions** that have occurred in past warm and cold climates, focusing on proxy data synthesis and synchronization of different records.
2. To derive probabilistic time series representations of proxy records that allow for a mathematically rigorous propagation of dating uncertainties to subsequent analysis such as synchronization and dependency analyses between different records, search for **EWS**, but also the model evaluations planned in WP2.
3. To assess interactions between different **TEs**, and the ecological and societal impacts of past **abrupt climate transitions**. This will provide valuable information for estimating the impacts of potentially similar events due to global warming in the future.
4. To extend existing concepts of statistical **EWSs** in paleoclimatic proxy records by advancing the employed statistical estimators and taking into account associated physical mechanisms. This will provide detailed information regarding the specific subsystems and statistical characteristics in which **EWSs** for potential future **abrupt transitions** should be searched for.

WP2: Modelling of tipping elements in past climate

1. To assess the **climate stability** of a suite of state-of-the-art climate models. These are the **EMICs** Bern3D, CLIMBER-X, and FAMOUS, as well as the **ESMs** CESM, HadCM3, and UKESM1. This goal primarily feeds into TiPES Objective 1.
2. In delivering this assessment on **model stability**, to ensure that all WP2 work has the maximum positive impact on, and contribution to, the IPCC process.
3. To implement proxies directly in models to ensure that they can be evaluated against the WP1 datasets. This will help maintain European leadership in the research area of **ESM isotope code development**.

WP3: Modelling of tipping elements in present and future climate

1. To assess the risk of an **AMOC** shutdown in the near future due to global warming, and to identify corresponding **EWSs** from simulations.
2. To quantify the risk that the **Amazon rainforest** will tip to a savannah state due to global-warming-induced precipitation changes and due to deforestation, to identify **EWSs** for such a transition, and to provide an assessment of the climatological, ecological and socio-economic impacts of a potential dieback of the Amazon.

3. To estimate the response of the **Indian summer monsoon** to various scenarios of regional and global forcings in order to allow to define safe operating spaces that exclude future dangerous conditions in the hydroclimatology of the region, and to quantify **EWSs** of a potential regime shift of the monsoon.
4. To assess the impacts of **TP** crossings on a range of relevant climate properties in Europe, such as the statistics of atmospheric blocking, weather regimes and extremes, to identify worst case scenarios in this regard, and to establish associated **EWS**.
5. To constrain the stability and future ice-sheet evolution in the mid-long term of the **Antarctic** and **Greenland ice sheets**, and to identify suitable **precursor signals** of a future stability loss.

WP4: Climate sensitivity and response

1. To extend the concept of **climate sensitivity** in order to systematically allow for state-dependent feedbacks, a large set of climatic observables, and multiple spatial and temporal scales.
2. To incorporate the effect of **TPs** in defining **climate sensitivity**.

WP5: Theoretical underpinning of tipping points

1. To understand the robustness of **TPs** across the **climate model hierarchy**.
2. To further develop and apply non-autonomous dynamical systems theory appropriate to understand climate **tipping phenomena** in the presence of a variety of **GHG emissions scenarios**.
3. To develop and evaluate novel **early warning signals (EWS)** for non-autonomous climate problems and associated statistical forecasting and detection tests.